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Uncertainty in niche assessment: a solution to the dilemma redundancy vs. exclusion

1 **Title:** Uncertainty principle in niche assessment: a solution to the dilemma redundancy vs. competitive exclusion, and
 2 some analytical consequences.

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21 **Abstract.**

22 There has been a categorically unresolved crucial question in ecology and evolutionary theory for many decades;
 23 perhaps from the times of Charles Darwin himself: Is it possible, under natural conditions, that two species can perform
 24 a commonly shared ecological niche? There are two extreme conventional responses that have kept divided the
 25 scientific community in this regard for almost forty years: **(a)** No; that is to say, the well-known competitive exclusion
 26 principle (CEP). **(b)** Yes; that is to say, the well-known hypothesis of full functional redundancy (HFR). Obviously, the
 27 reliability of both responses depends on an underlying and even more essential requisite: that the ecological niche of a
 28 given species can be assessed with such accuracy as we could want in order to detect the degree in which it is shared
 29 between coexisting species. This article is the seventh in a continuous series of interconnected recent publications that
 30 promotes an alternative understanding of ecology and evolutionary biology which is in favor of strong and mutually
 31 fruitful analytical links between biology and physics. This article analyzes the statistical behavior of ecological niches
 32 by taking into account two indicators that are essential to perform the ecological niche of all species: species diversity
 33 per plot (H_p) and eco-kinetic energy (E_e) as a proxy for trophic energy in a scalar field H_p , E_e in which an oscillating
 34 performance of ecological niches is deployed. According to our results, in the same measurement in which the accuracy
 35 of H_p assessments increases (reduction of H_p 's standard deviation: σ_{H_p}) the accuracy of E_e assessment decreases
 36 (increment of σ_{E_e}), and vice versa, in agreement with a pattern that is completely equivalent to that of the Heisenberg's
 37 uncertainty principle in quantum mechanics (i.e.: $\sigma_{H_p} \cdot \sigma_{E_e} \gg \frac{1}{2} h_e^{ec} / 2\pi$; where h_e^{ec} : ecological equivalent of Planck's
 38 constant found in previous publications). As a result, the ecological niche is, even in principle in addition to in practice,

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39 indeterminable with enough exactness to arrive to a categorical response to the above-stated question. This means that
40 CEP and HFR are simultaneously true and false in the same measure, because the only feasible option to keep the
41 functional stability of ecosystems is a wave-like combination of both options: when species are pushed to a high degree
42 of coexistence (increase of partition of the gradient) in regard to H_p values (a trend in favor of HFR), their degree of
43 coexistence in regard to E_e values diminishes (decrease of partition of the E_e gradient, a trend in favor of CEP), and vice
44 versa. The final sections of the article highlight the eco-evolutionary, biogeographical and socio-economic meaning of
45 this result, by offering plausible alternative explanations to a wide spectrum of phenomena that appear to be only
46 partially understood so far, e.g.: the contradictory results about the relationship between body size, species diversity and
47 macroevolutionary rates; the general environmental scenario in favor of macroevolutionary leaps with a low probability
48 to leave footprints in the fossil record; the unnecessary, although stimulant, influence of geographic isolation to promote
49 evolutionary changes; the island rule; and the general meaning of the interaction between nature and society.

50

51 **Keywords:** competitive exclusion; ecological niche; ecological state equation; ecological equivalent of Planck's
52 constant; functional redundancy; uncertainty principle.

53

54 1. Introduction

55 The conventional statement of competitive exclusion principle (CEP) holds that perfect competitors (complete niche
56 overlap) cannot coexist (Hardin, 1960). CEP, or Gause's principle (Volterra, 1926; 1931; Gause, 1934a, b), dates back
57 to The Origin of Species (Darwin, 1859), where it was already implicit (Hardin, 1960). The first explicit statement of
58 CEP is attributed to Grinnell (1904). According to some authors, CEP is one of the most important laws in ecology and
59 evolution (e.g., Hardin, 1960; Whittaker, 1965; Darlington 1972; Gordon, 2000; Wang et al., 2005). In contrast, others
60 believe that CEP is an oversimplification that contradicts observed reality, and its contribution to our understanding of
61 nature is not commensurate with its degree of widespread acceptance (e.g., Savile, 1960; Ayala, 1969; den Boer, 1986;
62 Stanley, 2008).

63 Certainly, close coexistence of similar species of plants (e.g., Shmida and Ellner, 1984; Hubbell, 1979; 2006;
64 Silvertown, 2004) is, at least, paradoxical. One would expect such coexistence to be rapidly dissolved under the
65 influence of CEP. If this dissolution does not occur in practice, then there is a hard argument against CEP. The need to
66 explain this paradox has led to the hypothesis of functional redundancy (HFR or FR, hereafter). This hypothesis, as well
67 as other approaches derived from it, such as the unified neutral theory of biodiversity and biogeography (Hubbell,
68 2005), offers alternative interpretations to CEP in an attempt to compensate for its apparent limitations. According to
69 HFR, many species in the ecosystem act as spare parts for each other, providing information that is repeated and
70 exceeds the amount needed to maintain the viability of the system (see, e.g.: Naeem, 1998; Rosendfeld, 2002a, p.
71 156). What really matters, from the point of view of HFR, it is the existence of functional groups: a group of species
72 that are interlinked due to the equivalent exploitation of the same resource, the consumption of which is optional in
73 other species, or humans. Thus the function of a given species that disappears is easily offset by another species of the
74 same functional group (Naeem, 1998; Clarke and Warwick, 1998; Mistri et al., 2001). Functional groups with few
75 species are more susceptible to extinction due to their low capability of internal replacement (Holling, 1986). Therefore,
76 conservation of these functional groups must be a priority (Walker, 1992). As a result, FR has been equated to surplus
77 of resources (see Lawton and Brown, 1993). FR could explain why changes in species diversity, within certain broad

78 limits, do not change the essential functioning of the ecosystem (Loreau, 2004); because, very frequently, there could be
79 a total functional equivalence between species.

80 Despite the current influence of this debate (see Palma, 2010) its point of origin is very old, very important, as well
81 as rooted in the deepest foundations of contemporary ecology (see Lewin, 1983). It is probable that several wide
82 reviews (e.g., Rosenfeld, 2002a, b; Petchey and Gaston, 2006) and additional explanations based on inter-branches links
83 in ecology (e.g., Mayfield and Levine, 2010) have drained the conventional viewpoint about this subject. However,
84 since the debate continues, it seems to be that a more comprehensive alternative explanation could be suitable.

85 From time to time, an old scientific debate needs to be updated due to some recent findings that pose the same old
86 question in a new perspective. This is the first objective of this article. From our point of view, the cornerstone of the
87 debate HFR vs. CEP lies in a wider and deeper question. Since both trends (either HFR or CEP) have a common origin
88 in responding if a given ecological niche can be performed in a shared way or not, respectively (this is one of the oldest
89 questions in ecology), then the essential question that reflects the main objective of this article is the following: Is it
90 possible to define in practice a given ecological niche in a way exact enough as to know if it is being performed in a
91 shared way, or not? Besides, since an explanation based on physics could be little attractive to some biologists, the
92 second objective of this article is to establish links, as abundant as possible, between our main results and well-known
93 eco-evolutionary issues in order to support the usefulness of this approach for conventional ecological thinking.

94 Section 2.1 offers a theoretical panorama of recent findings that are used in Section 2.2 to expose the methodology
95 applied. Section 3 exposes our main results in this regard. Sections 4.1 to 4.2 analyze the meaning of our results in
96 order to answer the central question posed in the previous paragraph. If this response is *positive* (i.e., there is not
97 uncertainty in niche assessment) the debate HFR vs. CEP will remain as so far, without a clear solution. On the
98 contrary, if this response is *negative* (i.e., there is uncertainty in niche assessment), then the main conclusion is that this
99 old and acrimonious debate is nonsense either because (a): the common-root concept (ecological niche) for CEP and
100 HFR is, even in principle in addition to in practice, indeterminable with enough exactness to arrive to a categorical
101 response; or because (b): the functional coupling between CEP and FR is the unique feasible solution to keep the
102 stability of ecosystem functioning. Finally, Section 4.3 explores the consequences of our results by means of empirical
103 examples and alternative explanations to well-known eco-evolutionary problems, in order to achieve the second
104 objective mentioned in the previous paragraph. Albeit the core content of this article is exposed in Sections 2 to 4.2,
105 Section 4.3 is perhaps the most interesting of all of them for the readers of this journal due to its strong connections with
106 the classical point of view about ecology, evolution, biogeography and biological conservation.

107

108 **2. Theoretical foundation and methods**

109 *2.1 An analytically evolving theoretical framework, including all the essential physical principles for* 110 *ecologists*

111 A branch of ecological analysis based on a greening of an old foundational proposal has grown in the last 3 years
112 (2012–2015). That is to say, ecology can be understood, in the last instance, as a set of emergent properties starting
113 from physics (see, e.g., Lindeman, 1942; Odum, 1968, 1969; Gallucci, 1973; Bugmann and Martin, 1995). So the
114 essential traits of ecosystem functioning could be backward-assembled until reaching their primordial contact points
115 with physics. Starting from this cornerstone assumption, species diversity (measured as H , see Eq. (1), below) has been
116 successfully used as the main state variable to obtain:

117 (1) An ecological state equation (Rodríguez et al., 2012; see Eq. (2), below) that is structurally equivalent to the
 118 ideal gas state equation (Eq. (3)), and it is always valid providing that in the analyzed ecosystem the energy input is in
 119 balance or quasi-balance with the respective output (i.e., under stationary or quasi-stationary ecological conditions).

120 (2) An ecological extension (Eq. (8)) of the Boyle-Mariotte law (Eq. (9)) which implies that it is impossible to
 121 increase trophic productivity (expressed as the amount of available energy per kg of biomass: E_{eTp}/m_{ep} , see below)
 122 without reducing species diversity (Rodríguez et al., 2013b). That is to say, the ecological succession goes from i to 1 in
 123 Eq. (8) meanwhile the economic exploitation of natural resources goes in the other way around.

124 (3) A sprout of theoretical solution to the issue analyzed in this article, by means of a stationary waves model of
 125 species coexistence based on a sequence of transient equilibrium nodes of CEP and wide antinodes of limited FR (in a
 126 similar way to the standing waves on a string; see Rodríguez et al., 2013b).

$$127 \quad H = -\sum_{i=1}^S \left[\left(\frac{n_i}{N} \right) \left(\ln \frac{n_i}{N} \right) \right], \quad (1)$$

128 where S : species number, n_i : number of individuals of species i , $N = \sum n_i$. H is conventionally expressed in nat/individual
 129 when natural logarithms are used (see Shannon, 1948; Magurran, 2004).

$$130 \quad 2N_p \left(\frac{1}{2} m_{ep} I_e^2 \right) = \frac{(N_p k_e)}{H_p}; \quad \text{or} \quad 2E_{eTp} = \frac{(N_p k_e)}{H_p} \quad (2)$$

131 where H_p : ecological information (Eq. (1)) assessed as species diversity per plot; k_e : ecological equivalent of Boltzmann
 132 constant (k_B). $k_e = m_{ep} \cdot I_e^2 \cdot H_p = 1.3806504E\varphi J_e \cdot \text{nat/individual}$, this parameter indicates the average rate in which an
 133 individual exchanges H by E_e across the set of plots under stationary ecological conditions; $\varphi = -x_i, \dots, -3, -2, -1, 0, +1,$
 134 $+2, +3, \dots, +x_i$, depending on the type of taxocenosis studied (see examples of typical values of φ in Rodríguez et al.,
 135 2013b); N_p , m_{ep} , and E_{eTp} : see Eq. (4); I_e : see Eq. (5).

$$136 \quad 2N \left(\frac{1}{2} m v^2 \right) = N k_B T \quad (3)$$

137 where N : number of molecules; m : molecular mass; v : molecular velocity; k_B : physical Boltzmann constant and T :
 138 absolute temperature.

$$139 \quad E_{eTp} = N_p (E_{ep}) = N_p \left(\frac{1}{2} m_{ep} I_e^2 \right) = \frac{1}{2} m_{eTp} I_e^2 \quad (4)$$

140 where N_p : number of individuals per plot; E_{eTp} : total eco-kinetic energy per plot (Rodríguez et al., 2012; 2013a, b;
 141 2015a, b); E_{ep} : mean eco-kinetic energy per individual per plot (p) expressed in eco-Joule (J_e ; about the meaning of this
 142 unit, see Appendix A, Section 2); m_{ep} : mean biomass per individual per plot; m_{eTp} : total biomass per plot (p); I_e : dispersal
 143 indicator (expressed in \bar{d} units, see Eq. (5), below) with the appropriate features to replace v (physical velocity) in an
 144 interdisciplinary invariant way in regard to the replacement of T by H from Eq. (3) to Eq. (2). Appendix A, section 1,
 145 includes expanded explanations about the characteristics and meaning of I_e according to Rodríguez et al. (2013a).

$$146 \quad I_e = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^S (I_{e,i,j})}{S} \quad (5)$$

$$147 \quad I_{e,i,j} = \left(\frac{d_{i,j}}{\sigma_{i,j}} \right) \times 100 \quad (6)$$

$$d_{i,j} = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^m \left(\sqrt{(x_j - x_k)^2 + (y_j - y_k)^2} \right) \times \left(2i_{j,k} / (i_j + i_k) \right)}{m} \quad (7)$$

148 where $d_{i,j}$ is the mean dispersal activity of species i in plot j with central geographic coordinates x, y within a total space
 149 s_0 divided into an m number of k plots; i_j and i_k are the respective abundances of i in plots j and k ; $i_{j,k}$ is the shared
 150 number of individuals of i in plots j and k (e.g., if $i_j = 7$ and $i_k = 12$, then $i_{j,k} = 7$); $2i_{j,k}/(i_j+i_k)$ is the Bray-Curtis similarity
 151 index (Washington, 1984); $\sigma_{i,j}$ is the standard deviation of $d_{i,j}$ given that $d_{i,j}$ is an arithmetic mean; $I_{e,i,j}$ is the dispersal
 152 indicator of species i in plot j ; I_e is the dispersal indicator of the species group in plot j ; and S is the species number in
 153 plot j . $\sqrt{(x_j - x_k)^2 + (y_j - y_k)^2}$ is the Pythagorean theorem that allows the estimation of a mean Euclidean distance between
 154 plot j and all the remaining k elements within the set of m plots.

$$156 P_{e(s)1} \cdot V_{e(s)1} \cdot H_{T1} = P_{e(s)2} \cdot V_{e(s)2} \cdot H_{T2} =_{3, 4, 5, \dots, i}, \text{ or, in statistical mechanical equivalent terms,} \quad (8)$$

$$157 \left(\frac{m_{eTp} \cdot I_e^2}{s_0} \right)_1 \times \left(\frac{s_0}{m_{eTp}} \right)_1 \times H_{T1} = \left(\frac{m_{eTp} \cdot I_e^2}{s_0} \right)_2 \times \left(\frac{s_0}{m_{eTp}} \right)_2 \times H_{T2} =_{3, 4, 5, \dots, i}$$

158 where $P_{e(s)}$: specific ecological pressure; $V_{e(s)}$: specific ecological volume; H_T : total diversity –expressed in
 159 nat/individual, with $H_{T1} > H_{T2} > H_{T3} > \dots > H_{Ti}$ – of the survey (or the iso- H_T hyperbolic curve in a chart of $P_{e(s)}$ vs. $V_{e(s)}$)
 160 that embraces the set of plots for which the values of $P_{e(s)}$ and $V_{e(s)}$ per plot have been calculated; s_0 : mean space (either
 161 area or volume) per plot in meters.

$$162 \frac{(P_1 \cdot V_1)}{T_1} = \frac{(P_2 \cdot V_2)}{T_2} =_{3, 4, 5, \dots, i}, \text{ or, in statistical mechanical equivalent terms,} \quad (9)$$

$$163 \frac{(2N \frac{1}{2} m v^2)}{T_1} = \frac{(2N \frac{1}{2} m v^2)}{T_2} =_{3, 4, 5, \dots, i}$$

164 where P : gas pressure; V : gas volume; T : absolute temperature in K (i.e., temperature of the respective hyperbolic
 165 isotherm in a chart P vs. V , with $T_1 < T_2 < T_3 < \dots < T_i$) that embraces the set of gas samples for which the values of P
 166 and V have been calculated; m : molecular mass in kg; N : number of molecules of the gas sample; v : mean value of the
 167 square velocity per molecule in m/s.

168 That is to say, from item (1) (above) and Eq. (2), stationary ecological conditions are kept by a biomass-dispersal
 169 trade-off in function of diversity values (B-D_{TO-H}: either $m_{ep} \downarrow, I_e^{2\uparrow}, H_p \downarrow$ or, alternatively: $m_{ep} \uparrow, I_e^{2\downarrow}, H_p \uparrow$, and this triple
 170 combination of decreasing \downarrow and increasing \uparrow variables supports the constant value of $k_e = m_{ep} \cdot I_e^2 \cdot H_p$ at the large
 171 scale within the ecosystem). This exchange, in turn, guarantees that any stationary ecosystem behaves just as a lab
 172 balloon that contains a gas at a constant temperature, in spite of the absence of any kind of tangible walls in the
 173 ecological context. That is to say, there is a deficit of eco-kinetic energy ($E_{ep} = \frac{1}{2} m_{ep} I_e^2$) in both edges of the H_p gradient
 174 either because biomass is low (at low H_p values), or because I_e^2 is low (at high H_p values). Then $m_{ep} \cdot I_e^2 \cdot H_p = k_e$ pushes
 175 the set of plots toward a thermo-statistical accretion center at the point of maximum probability (mode) of H_p values
 176 within a sort of dynamic cage or ecological cavity resonator with invisible but effective limits. This resonator combines
 177 maximum eco-kinetic energy values per plot with intermediate species diversity values (i.e., from the above-commented
 178 B-D_{TO-H}: $(m_{ep} \cdot I_e^2)_{max.} \leftrightarrow$ intermediate values of H_p).

179 Within an ecological cavity resonator, the oscillations of trophic indicators across a gradient of H_p values tend to
 180 become a pair of stationary trophic information waves. These waves bounce back and forth between the two opposite
 181 edges of the ecological cavity resonator (from $m_{ep} \downarrow, I_e^{2\uparrow}, H_p \downarrow$ to $m_{ep} \uparrow, I_e^{2\downarrow}, H_p \uparrow$, and vice versa) interfering with each

182 other; in a similar way to a guitar string that vibrates fixed at both ends. Every stationary trophic information wave has
183 antinodes (points of maximum wave amplitude, $A_w \rightarrow \max.$) as well as nodes (equilibrium points in which $A_w = 0$ due to
184 the interaction between both waves traveling in opposite directions). According to Rodríguez et al. (2013b) this
185 alternate succession of antinodes and nodes produces the above-mentioned stationary waves model of species
186 coexistence. Since “the so-called ‘competitive exclusion principle’ states that, **at equilibrium**, the number of coexisting
187 species cannot be larger than the number of resources for which they compete” (Bracco et al., 2000, p. 1795); then the
188 CEP only would work at the node level and the HFR (either in a partial or in a full way) only would work at the
189 antinode level (Rodríguez et al., 2013b). In such a way, both options would work, connected to each other, by reaching
190 higher levels of ecological regulation (nodes are very tiny and transient points impervious to the flow of energy, then
191 they can work as barriers to avoid lethal competition levels) as well as higher levels of species coexistence (at the level
192 of wide antinodes). The above-summarized stationary waves model of species coexistence had two main problems in
193 2013: **(1)** it suggested that the ecosystem should deploy certain quantum traits in connection with the HFR \leftrightarrow CEP
194 debate (e.g.: “the idea [of the CEP] may suggest another idea from across the sciences –the principle of Pauli, that no
195 two electrons occupy the same atomic ‘niche’”; Whittaker, 1965, p. 258). These traits would emerge from the
196 combination between the above-mentioned wave-like model of coexistence and the non-continuous (discrete) variation
197 of k_e (see comments in regard to φ in Eq. (2)), since energy has a discontinuous nature in quantum mechanics. However,
198 there was no empirical evidence in this regard in that moment. **(2)** The specific nature of the above-mentioned
199 stationary trophic information waves was a conundrum.

200 About problem **(1)**: Rodríguez et al. (2015b) found, at the inter-taxocenosis scale, that a significant and robust
201 straight line adjustment ($r = 0.9923$, $p = 2.13E-22$; with the intercept at 0,0) between the mean value of E_e at the survey
202 level and k_e has a regression constant (slope) whose mantissa coincides with the Planck’s constant (h) mantissa at the
203 1000th level. That is to say, starting from the microscopic root of the evolutionary tree there has been an initial clot of
204 life (with a given initial tiny value of eco-kinetic energy = $E_{e(i)}$) that has been ecologically driven across a step by step
205 evolutionary gradient ($\Sigma \nabla k_e$) of exchange of information by eco-kinetic energy at a constant eco-kinetic energy
206 increment rate of h_e^{ev} (i.e., the evolutionary quantum of action from the point of view of trophodynamics at the inter-
207 taxocenosis scale = $6.62606957E-01 J_e$) per each value of $\nabla k_e = 1J_e \cdot \text{nat}/\text{individual}$. About problem **(2)**: Rodríguez et al.
208 (2015c) found that the ecological relationship summarized by Eq. (10), starting from a simple replacement of variables
209 in the original quantum relationship summarized by Eq. (11) (Halliday et al., 1999, and Tipler and Mosca, 2010¹),
210 yields a value of $h_e^{ec} = 6.62606957E\varphi J_e \cdot \text{nat}/\text{individual}$: the ecological quantum of action at the intra-taxocenosis scale,
211 or the minimum and discrete (non-continuous) mean value of eco-kinetic energy per individual that can be exchanged
212 per each information unit across a species diversity gradient within an ecosystem under stationary ecological conditions.
213 The method applied to obtain this result is summarized in Fig. 1 starting from an empirical example based on real data.
214 In regard to Fig. 1: energy must be retained as much as possible in between nodes of CEP that are impervious to energy
215 flow in order to attain a consumption of energy as efficient as possible. However, due to the same reason, energy flow
216 between antinodes would be impossible at all with an immovable sequence of nodes. Hence the ecosystem performs
217 fluctuations throughout a sequences of overtones (e.g.: $o_i = 1 \leftrightarrow 2 \leftrightarrow 3, \dots \leftrightarrow \dots 16$ from Fig. 1e1 to 1e2, and vice versa)
218 by achieving in such a way a retention of flow of eco-kinetic energy across an ever-changing sequence of antinodes of
219 limited FR in order to feed the all of the ecosystem elements.

¹ All the comments about conventional physical principles in this article without citing a particular source are supported by principles, methods and concepts exposed in any of these two books.

$$h_e^{ec} = \lambda_{eM} \cdot p_{eM} = \lambda_{eM} \cdot (m_{eM} \cdot I_{eM}) \quad (10)$$

221 where: λ_{eM} : ecological wavelength per individual per macrostate (M) per survey expressed in ΔH_p ' values (see Fig. 1b
 222 and 1c); H_p ': class mark (midpoint) per class of values into a statistical distribution of H_p values; p_{eM} : mean ecological
 223 momentum per individual per macrostate; m_{eM} : mean individual biomass per macrostate; I_{eM} : mean value of Eq. (5) at
 224 the macrostate level; M : a given set of plots included into one of the categories or class of values within a discontinuous
 225 (i.e.: with a class width tiny enough as to produce a non-continuous succession of H_p classes within the distribution)
 226 statistical density distribution of species diversity values per plot (H_p) for a given survey.

$$h = \lambda \cdot p = \lambda \cdot (m \cdot v) \quad (11)$$

228 where: h : Planck's constant = 6.62606957E-34 J·s; λ : wavelength of the "pilot wave" associated to a given atomic
 229 particle; p : momentum; m : atomic particle mass; v : atomic particle velocity.

230 Physics is an experimental and positivist science. Only those parameters which can be empirically measured in order
 231 to perform experimental tests have a reliable meaning in physics. As a result, any concept or physical law depends on
 232 an observation (understood it as a measurement event) as exact as possible. The quantum uncertainty principle (a.k.a.:
 233 Heisenberg's uncertainty principle or Heisenberg's indetermination principle) is one of the main pillars of quantum
 234 mechanics. The quantum uncertainty principle embraces a variety of mathematical inequalities asserting a fundamental
 235 limit to the precision with which certain pairs of physical properties (let us to say, Θ and Ω , a.k.a. complementary
 236 variables) of a particle can be measured simultaneously. In physics, the most common set of variables for Θ are position
 237 and time (t), meanwhile the most common set of variables for Ω are momentum and kinetic energy (E ; see Eq. (12) in
 238 comparison with E_{ep} in Eq. (4)), respectively.

$$E = \frac{1}{2}mv^2 \quad (12)$$

240 The simplest statement of quantum uncertainty principle is:

$$\sigma_{\Theta} \cdot \sigma_{\Omega} \geq \left(0.5\hbar = 0.5 \frac{h}{2\pi} \right) \quad (13)$$

242 where: σ_{Θ} : standard deviation of the observed values of Θ (either position or *time*); σ_{Ω} : standard deviation of the
 243 observed values of Ω (either momentum or *kinetic energy*: E , see Eq. (12)); \hbar : reduced Planck's constant, or Dirac's
 244 constant = $h/2\pi$; h : Planck's constant; π : 3.14159...; and $0.5 \cdot \hbar = \frac{1}{2}h/2\pi = 5.27286E-35$ if the value of physical constant
 245 Planck is the used one. In fact, quantum uncertainty is usually very higher than $0.5 \cdot \hbar$.

246 At a more general scale, the quantum uncertainty principle can be understood as a quantum law connected to the
 247 laws of thermodynamics given the opposite relationship between information and entropy (see, among many others:
 248 Rothstein, 1952; Tribus, 1961; Gallucci, 1973; Brissaud, 2005; Tiezzi and Pulselli, 2008) as well as the formal
 249 equivalence between information and reduction of uncertainty, since uncertainty (as lack of information) and entropy
 250 are essential identical to each other (see, e.g.: Lewis, 1930, p. 573; Gabor, 1964; Ayres, 1994, p. 36). For example, in
 251 the case of Eq. (13), our gaining of information about the particle state in regard to variable Θ means an automatic
 252 increase of our lack of information (increase of uncertainty or entropy) about the state of the same particle in regard to
 253 variable Ω , and vice versa. As a result, it is impossible to reduce entropy (uncertainty) to zero (third law of
 254 thermodynamics or Nernst's Principle) in agreement with $\sigma_{\Theta} \cdot \sigma_{\Omega} \geq 0.5 \cdot \hbar$. In such a way all physical laws become
 255 information functions collected according to various procedures (see Rothstein, 1951, p. 173).

256 According to previous commented results (Rodríguez et al., 2013b; 2015b, c; see comments above) this article is
 257 based on a study performed in order to prove if:

$$\sigma_{\Theta_e} \cdot \sigma_{\Omega_e} \geq \left(0.5\hbar^{ec} = 0.5 \frac{h^{ec}}{2\pi} \right) \quad (14)$$

where Θ_e and Ω_e is a pair of ecological indicators (σ_{H_p} : standard deviation of the midpoint per category in the statistical distribution of species diversity values, and σ_{E_e} : standard deviation of mean eco-kinetic energy per individual per category in the statistical distribution of diversity values, respectively; see below) that are complementary to each other (analytically equivalent to E and t in the previous physical example), and h_e^{ec} : see Eq. (10). h_e^{ec} 's values for the surveys explored in this article were calculated by Rodríguez et al. (2015c). Let us suppose that Eq. (14) is positively proven. Hence, the debate HFR vs. CEP makes no sense because the common-root concept (ecological niche) for both alternatives is indeterminable with enough exactness to arrive to a categorical response about this subject.

Firstly, the replacement of E in Eq. (13) by an equivalent ecological variable in order to obtain Eq. (14) does not seem to be a big problem since Eq. (4) includes the calculation of eco-kinetic energy (E_e), and it has a homomorphic structure in comparison with E (Eq. (12)). Secondly, species diversity (Eq. (1)) seem to be the most appropriate variable to replace t in Eq. (13), since the increase of H is regarded as the most conspicuous, widespread and stable time trend of ecological succession in the long run. That is to say, it is well-known that the simultaneous increase of H and its associated parameters (species richness and evenness) over time is a general trait in nature (Margalef, 1963; Odum, 1968; 1969; Gordon, 2000, p. 193). In other words, if H and t go hand by hand in the large scale along the successional process, then there should not be any obstacle with the replacement of t by H .

In addition, the ecological complementarity between these variables involves several traits that are especially suitable to resolve the debate HFR vs. CEP via quantum uncertainty principle:

- 1) It is well-known (see Rosenfeld, 2002a, b; Petchey and Gaston, 2006; Boersma et al., 2013) that using many traits to completely describe ecological niches produces a lower probability of FR and, contrastingly, a higher probability of CEP, and vice versa; simply because the probability of finding inter-species differences (a result in favor of CEP) increases with the number of traits. Therefore, if we want to explore if the dilemma CEP vs. HFR is untenable or not, the number of variables should remain as small as possible. That is to say, if an insurmountable uncertainty level about the assessment of ecological niche is detected even by using only two variables (it is the minimum dimensionality in this context; i.e.: a bidimensional scalar space H_p, E_e), then it is clear that this uncertainty level will be greater and greater in the same measure in which more and more variables would be included.
- 2) *“For functional classifications, there should be no target number of traits, rather the correct number of traits is the number that are functionally important”* (Petchey and Gaston, 2006, p. 744). It is difficult to deny the importance of the variables selected in this case: On the one hand, trophic energy (E_e) is the basic support to all of the activities deployed by every species within the ecosystem. On the other hand, H defines the potential width of the total set of probable interspecific interactions between a given species and its biotic environment as a whole.
- 3) A given pair of variables used with this goal should not have exceptions. That is to say, it should produce an analytical space capable to encompass any kind of species. It is evident that there are no possible exceptions in regard to the combination of species diversity and energy since every species depends on an ecological context with energy and other species.
- 4) Since we applied an analytical algorithm based on interdisciplinary connections, then the pair of selected variables in order to prove the ecological QUP in practice needs to be simultaneously coherent with ecology and

297 physics. The structural equivalence between Eq. (2) and Eq. (3) as well as between Eq. (4) and Eq. (12)
298 supports the above-mentioned interdisciplinary coherence.

299 2.2 Specific methods to test quantum ecological uncertainty

300 We explored data collected from 24 surveys (for a total of 750 species and 88701067 individuals) belonging to 11
301 different types of taxocenes (*cor*: massive –non-branching– corals, Veracruz coast, Gulf of Mexico; *crf*: coral reef
302 fishes; Veracruz coast, Gulf of Mexico; *css*: coastal succulent shrub vegetation, Tenerife Island, Spain; *lli*: litter
303 invertebrates in laurisilva, Tenerife Island, Spain; *ma*: marine microalgae, Guadalquivir Marshes, Seville, Spain. *mif*:
304 marine interstitial meiofauna of sandy beaches, Tenerife Island, Spain; *Ms*: Mediterranean shrub vegetation, Andalusia,
305 Spain; *mxs*: mixed shrub’s succulent vegetation, Tenerife Island, Spain; *pli*: litter invertebrates in pine forest, Tenerife
306 Island, Spain; *rsn*: tropical rocky shore snails, Manatee Harbor, northeast coast of Cuba; *rv*: ruderal vegetation, Tenerife
307 Island, Spain). Appendix A, Section 3, includes detailed explanations about sampling methods and associated
308 indicators. The equality posed by Eq. (2) in order to prove if a taxocenosis is under stationary ecological conditions was
309 tested in every survey by means of the appropriate test of mean comparison.

310 The methodology to obtain the h_e^{ec} value (Eq. (10)) per statistical distribution of H_p values per survey, explained in
311 Fig. 1, was applied to all of the surveys until reach: mean maximum number of statistical distributions of H_p values per
312 survey of 38.75; mean minimum number of microstates –plots– per macrostate – H_p class– of 2.452 per survey; and
313 mean value of the width of H_p class expressed as % of the maximum ΔH_p per statistical distributions of H_p values of
314 2.544 % per survey; in order to explore a range of overtone as wide as possible (from $o_i = 1$ –fundamental harmonic at
315 f_o – to a mean maximum value of $o_i = 16.636$ per survey; where o_i : overtone number).

316 The values of σ_{E_e} and σ_{H_p} (see Eq. (14)) from every set of macrostates per statistical distributions of H_p values per
317 survey were calculated and correlated: **(1)** with the overtone number (o_i) per statistical distributions of H_p values in
318 order to test if the quantum ecological uncertainty is associated to the system’s wave nature, or not, since λ_e decreases
319 with the increase of o_i , and vice versa; as well as **(2)** with each other (i.e., correlation σ_{E_e} vs. σ_{H_p}) in order to assess the
320 degree of trade-off between both standard deviations (i.e., quantum ecological uncertainty, properly speaking).

321 The mean value of $\sigma_{E_e} \cdot \sigma_{H_p}$ was compared (via *t*-Student test) with the respective value of $0.5 \cdot \hbar_e^{ec}$ (see Eq. (14)) per
322 taxocene in order to test the secondary requisite for the fulfillment of (i.e., that $\sigma_{E_e} \cdot \sigma_{H_p} \gg 0.5 \cdot \hbar_e^{ec}$).

323 The product $\sigma_{E_e} \cdot \sigma_{H_p}$ was also correlated with:

324 **(1)** The standard deviation of the ecological wavelength (σ_{λ_e}) in order to test if the quantum ecological uncertainty
325 can be compensated or reduced by taking ecological measurements at high overtones (shorter wavelengths) since,
326 according to Eq. (10), there is a close relationship between E_e , H_p and λ_e ; as well as with

327 **(2)** the mean number of species per macrosate (μS_M) per statistical distributions of H_p values with the goal of:

328 a) Assessing the sign of the relationship between quantum ecological uncertainty and species richness.

329 b) In the case of a reliable correlation between μS_M and $\sigma_{E_e} \cdot \sigma_{H_p}$, evaluating the threshold level (l_i) for which
330 the mean number of species per macrostate would live in certainty (*c*) conditions (S_c : estimated number of
331 species at the cutting level of $\sigma_{E_e} \cdot \sigma_{H_p}$ in which $\sigma_{E_e} \cdot \sigma_{H_p} = 0.5 \cdot \hbar_e^{ec}$ = border value between certainty and
332 uncertainty) by performing their respective ecological niches in agreement with an ultra-strong assumption
333 of the classical statement of CEP: that all the concurrent species would perform their respective ecological
334 niches with a null overlap with reference to the scalar space H_p , E_e . This procedure was performed by
335 means of the respective regression equation between μS_M and $\sigma_{E_e} \cdot \sigma_{H_p}$ per survey, by taking $\sigma_{E_e} \cdot \sigma_{H_p} =$

336 $0.5 \cdot \hat{h}_e^{ec}$ as an independent predictor value. That is to say, if the regression equation: $\mu S_M = a - (b \times$
 337 $(\sigma_{H_p} \cdot \sigma_{E_e}))$, where a : intercept and b : regression coefficient; then:
 338 $S_{c \text{ at } t} = a - (b \times (0.5 \cdot \hat{h}_e^{ec}))$. (15)

339 Finally, the rate of change of S_c with the progress of ecological succession was evaluated by means of the correlation
 340 between the total value of species diversity per survey (H_T), and the difference between S_c and the total value of species
 341 richness (S_T) expressed as percentage of the total species richness itself (see Eq. (16)).

$$342 S_u \% = \frac{S_T - S_c}{S_T} \times 100 \quad (16)$$

343 where $S_u\%$: percentage of species living in uncertainty conditions (i.e.: interval of μS_M values for which $\sigma_{E_e} \cdot \sigma_{H_p} >$
 344 $0.5 \cdot \hat{h}_e^{ec}$) per survey; S_T : total number of species per survey; S_c : species number in certainty conditions, that is to say,
 345 below the border value between certainty and uncertainty in which $\sigma_{E_e} \cdot \sigma_{H_p} = 0.5 \cdot \hat{h}_e^{ec}$ according to the regression
 346 equation from the correlation between μS_M and $\sigma_{E_e} \cdot \sigma_{H_p}$ (see above); and μS_M : mean number of species per macrostate
 347 statistical distributions of H_p values.

348

349 2.3 Specific methods to show the connection between quantum ecological uncertainty and conventional eco- 350 evolutionary theory.

351 The above-mentioned correlation between $S_u\%$ and H_T allows identifying three functional sections or “*stretches of*
 352 *life*” in regard to the performance of ecological niche. These stretches were delimited and commented in connection
 353 with a theoretical analysis of the concept of niche, by simultaneously profiling several micro-models for key
 354 interspecific relationships. Such models were empirically exemplified in Section 4.3.1 by using coral reefs data. Our
 355 gross result in favor of quantum uncertainty in the assessment of ecological niche requires a small-scale explanation.
 356 This started with tessellation graphs (Voronoi lines) based on the association between values of species diversity and
 357 values of eco-kinetic energy across overtone sequences. These charts produced the spontaneous emergence at random
 358 of degenerate ecological states partially isolated of their ecological background. The appropriate traits of these states to
 359 promote macroevolutionary leaps, without geographic isolation conditions, were analyzed.

360 The relationship between body size and evolutionary rate has been a long-debated issue. A correlation between the
 361 span of geological stages and the starting point of these stages showed a clear pattern of evolutionary rate acceleration.
 362 The analytical bias either in favor or against this acceleration depending on the indicator selected (ecological vs. genetic
 363 indicators, respectively) was tested by means of a χ^2 test based on results of previous publications. Consequently, it was
 364 proven that the influence of body size on evolutionary rate can be plausibly explained starting from the calculation of
 365 the correlation between body size and quantum ecological uncertainty ($\sigma_{E_e} \cdot \sigma_{H_p}$) transformed as stacking coefficient
 366 ($\sigma_{E_e} \times (1/\sigma_{H_p})$); i.e.: the capability of certain amount of information to sustain more a more energy with the increase of
 367 body size into a scalar field H_p (E_e), which proportionally increases with the value of h_e^{ec} within an evolutionarily
 368 iterative range of total species diversity per survey of $0 < H_T \leq 5.64$ nat/individual per taxocenosis.

369 Taken this result into account, the link between quantum ecological uncertainty and the island rule was quite
 370 probable. This link was explored beginning with the concept of “eco-pause” (a zone of inhabitability in the H_p , E_e
 371 scalar space) and its significantly larger relative size in insular ecosystems. The exploration of the connection between
 372 this result and the typical traits of island biogeography directly led to consider that the well-known acceleration of
 373 evolutionary processes in islands does not depend on the geographic isolation and subsequent genetic segregation of

374 populations *per se* (as it has been considered in the conventional evolutionary theory), but on a phenomenon of
 375 ecological diffraction between the above-mentioned stationary trophic information waves (see Section 2.1) that is
 376 reinforced by the amplified influence of islands as ecological cavity resonator (see Section 2.1) due to the strict spatial
 377 restriction of their ecosystems . Finally, it was analyzed why the socio-economic exploitation of natural resources is
 378 equivalent to a collapse of trophic information waves thanks to the nature-society interaction understood as a
 379 measurement in the quantum sense of the term. The results of these methods and their meaning were discussed in
 380 combination with the results of the methods explained in Section 2.2 due to the strong linkage between them.

381

382 **3. Results about quantum ecological uncertainty and its primary effects on theoretical ecology**

383 Appendix B includes the values of all the parameters commented in section 2.2. The above-commented procedures
 384 have been graphically exemplified in this section by using the survey “cor” (taxocenosis of massive coral reef; coast of
 385 Veracruz, Gulf of Mexico) as a typical general case, simply selected because it is the first one in the alphabetic
 386 ordination of the set of surveys. The values for the rest of the surveys are included in the respective tables (Tables 1C –
 387 5C; Appendix C) depending on the statistical procedure commented in this section with reference to “cor”, used as an
 388 iterative benchmark. According to columns W and AB in Table B.1, Appendix B; surveys mif2 and rv5 are clearly
 389 under non-stationary ecological conditions (i.e.: $k_{e(\text{observed value})} \neq k_{e(\text{expected value})}$, and $2E_{eTp} \neq (N_p k_e)/H_p$; see Eq. (2)),
 390 meanwhile survey rv4 is in a border line in this regard. All of the remaining surveys are under stationary conditions.

391 There is a positive and highly significant correlation between σ_{Ee} and o_t (Fig. 2a). There is a negative and highly
 392 significant correlation between σ_{Hp} and o_t (Fig. 2b). According to Table 1C (Appendix C) this trade-off between both
 393 variables in function of o_t has no exceptions, with $p > 0.05$ in only 2 of 44 cases ($p = 0.062$ for o_t , σ_{Ee} in “mif3”, and $p =$
 394 0.171 for o_t , σ_{Ee} in “rsn₁₋₃”). Obviously, given the results from Fig. 2a and 2b, there is a negative and highly significant
 395 correlation between σ_{Ee} and σ_{Hp} (Fig. 2c). Table 2C (Appendix C) shows that the correlation between σ_{Ee} and σ_{Hp} is
 396 also negative for all the remaining surveys, with $p < 0.05$ in 20 of 22 cases; with exceptions in “css” ($p = 0.096$) and
 397 “rsn₁₋₃” ($p = 0.175$).

398 Fig. 2d shows that the mean value of $\sigma_{Ee} \cdot \sigma_{Hp}$ is significantly higher than the threshold value that marks the border
 399 between ecological uncertainty and certainty (at $\mu S_M \leftrightarrow \sigma_{Ee} \cdot \sigma_{Hp} < 0.5 \cdot \hbar_e^{ec}$, see “*ultra-strong assumption of the classical*
 400 *statement of CEP*”, above). This pattern has no exceptions across the set of surveys as a whole (see Table 3C,
 401 Appendix C).

402 According to Fig. 2e, there is a negative and significant correlation between $\sigma_{Ee} \cdot \sigma_{Hp}$ and σ_{λ_e} . That is to say,
 403 ecological uncertainty *increases* with the *decrease* of σ_{λ_e} . Table 4C confirms that the correlation $\sigma_{Ee} \cdot \sigma_{Hp}$ vs. σ_{λ_e} is, in
 404 general, either negative, or non-significant; or both, with the exception of “mif2” and “rv5”, both surveys under non-
 405 stationary ecological conditions. As a result, the increase of accuracy regarding λ_e measurements does not compensate
 406 by the increase of quantum ecological uncertainty under stationary ecological conditions.

407 There is a negative and highly significant correlation between $\sigma_{Ee} \cdot \sigma_{Hp}$ and the mean number of species per
 408 macrostate (μS_M) per overtone or distribution of H_p values (see Fig. 3a). In this case, the threshold level (l_t) between
 409 certainty ($(\sigma_{Ee} \cdot \sigma_{Hp}, \mu S_M) < l_t$) and uncertainty ($(\sigma_{Ee} \cdot \sigma_{Hp}, \mu S_M) > l_t$) is indicated by the coordinate $0.5 \cdot \hbar_e^{ec}$, $S_c = 5.2728E-$
 410 $5, 16.5041$. That is to say, 86.86% (S_c in %) of the total number of species ($S_T = 19$) of this survey ($(16.504/19) \times 100 =$
 411 86.86%) would be living under conditions of ecological certainty in the performance of their respective ecological
 412 niches regarding the scalar space H_p , E_e taking into account that, *ceteris paribus*, $\sigma_{Ee} \cdot \sigma_{Hp} = 0.5 \cdot \hbar_e^{ec} = 52728E-5$.

413 Meanwhile, 13.136% ($S_T - S_c = S_u$; expressed as a percentage of S_T) of the total species richness of this survey (19 –
 414 $16.504 = 2.496$; $(2.496/19) \times 100 = 13.137\%$) is living under conditions of ecological uncertainty precisely because of
 415 $\sigma_{Ee} \cdot \sigma_{Hp} > (0.5 \cdot \hbar_e^{ec} = 1/2 \hbar_e^{ec} / 2\pi = 1/2 \cdot 6.62606957E-4 / 2\pi = 5.52728E-5)$. This pattern (i.e., a negative y/o significant
 416 correlation between μS_M and $\sigma_{Ee} \cdot \sigma_{Hp}$) was accomplished in 19 of 22 surveys. In 1 of the remaining 3 surveys there was
 417 no correlation at all, and it was positive and significant in 2 cases (surveys “mif3” and “mxs”, see Table 5C, Appendix
 418 C). In the case of “mxs”, this assemblage is a sub-taxocenosis of succulent vegetation selected from a more
 419 encompassing taxocenosis of mixed scrub. This could cause an alteration of the pattern because part of the connections
 420 between mxs and its ecological context are out of the study. The change of pattern in “mif3” has no explanation.

421 The average values of S_c and S_u across the set of surveys (Table 5C, last row) indicates that 60.33 % of species
 422 would be living under conditions of certainty (S_c) in regard to niche performance; meanwhile 39.67 % of species are
 423 living under conditions of uncertainty (S_u) in regard to niche performance. This result seems to be in favor of CEP, at
 424 least with reference to the range of total species diversity values per survey explored in this work ($1.255 \text{ nat/individual}$
 425 $\leq H_T \leq 3.355 \text{ nat/individual}$).

426 The correlation ($r = 0.513$, $p = 0.015$; Fig. 3b) between total species diversity per survey (H_T) and the percentage of
 427 species living under uncertainty conditions ($S_u\%$; see Eq. (16)) with intercept $a = -18.115$ has a slope (b : increase rate
 428 of $S_u\%$ per each nat/individual of H_T increment) of 25.471%. The respective regression equation is $S_u\% = -18.115 +$
 429 $25.471 \times H_T$. Therefore, with $S_u\% = 100$, $H_T = (100 + 18.115) / 25.471 = 4.637 \text{ nat/individual}$: the value of H_T in which
 430 the 100% of concurrent species would be living under uncertainty conditions. However, the respective t -test for $a = -$
 431 18.115 in regard to $r = 0.513$ yielded a result of $t = -0.8125$, $p = 0.4261 > 0.05$. That is to say, there is not a significant
 432 difference between the correlation with $a = -18.115$ and $a = 0$.

433 With $a = 0$; $r' = 0.88$, $p = 3.092E-8$, and the slope of $S_u\%$ decreases from 25.471 to 17.8782% per every
 434 nat/individual of H_T increase. By applying the respective regression equation ($S_u\% = 0 + 17.8782 \times H_T$), it is easy to
 435 assess (since $H_T = S_u\% \div 17.8782$) that the limit of total species diversity (H_T) per taxocenosis in which $S_u\% = 100\%$ is
 436 $5.593 \text{ nat/individual}$. If we improve this analysis even more, excluding “mif2” and “rv5” due to its non-stationary state,
 437 then $r' = 0.8721$, $p = 2.584E-7$;

438 Regression equation: $S_u\% = 0 + 17.7298\% \times H_T$, (17)

439 and $H_T = 100\% \div 17.549 = 5.640 \text{ nat/individuals}$: the value of species diversity in which $S_c \rightarrow 0$, $S_u \rightarrow S_T$, and $S_u\% \rightarrow$
 440 100% (see r' in Fig. 3b).

441 The above-assessed set of H_T values (4.637; 5.593; and 5.640) when $S_u\% \rightarrow 100\%$ are either around or slightly
 442 higher than the maximum values of H_T per taxocenosis empirically measured all over the world (e.g., Margalef, 1991, p.
 443 371: $H_{Tmax} \approx 5.0$; Kent and Coker, 1992: $H_{Tmax} \geq 4.5$; Tripathi et al., 2004, p. 248: $H_{Tmax} = 5.1$; Jorgensen and
 444 Svirezhev, 2004, p. 76: $H_{Tmax} \approx 5.0$; Awang et al., 2008, p. 19: $H_{Tmax} = 5.39$; Reddy and Ugle, 2008, p. 88: $H_{Tmax} =$
 445 5.5).

446

447 **4. Discussion and results about the secondary effects of quantum ecological uncertainty**

448 *4.1 The eco-evolutionary stretches of life from the point of view of quantum ecological uncertainty*

449 According to the results shown in Fig. 2, it is possible to infer two main outcomes: (a) The high and significant
 450 association of σ_{Ee} and σ_{Hp} , with σ , supports the idea that ecological uncertainty is closely associated to the wave nature
 451 of ecosystem functioning commented in regard to Fig. 1 (see Section 2). It is evident that in this case the “observer

452 effect” can be excluded as an alternative explanation to quantum ecological uncertainty since Fig. 2 has been obtained
453 starting from data of massive coral reefs that were collected with a null human interference on the ecological
454 performance of the observed organisms (see sampling methods in Appendix A, Section 3). **(b)** The results exemplified
455 by Fig. 2c are in full agreement with the expected pattern in the supposed case of a quantum uncertainty in the
456 assessment of ecological niche. This conclusion is additionally supported by the results shown in Fig. 2d and Table 3C
457 (i.e., $\sigma_{Hp} \cdot \sigma_{Ee} \gg 0.5 \cdot \hbar_e^{ec}$ in all of the surveys). Coherently, taking into account the structure of Eq. (10), the possibility of
458 reducing quantum ecological uncertainty by taking field observations in overtones in which the accuracy of λ_e
459 measurements is higher (low σ_{λ_e} values) is null according to Fig. 2e and Table 4C. As a result, within this analytical
460 framework at least, quantum ecological uncertainty has been positively tested. **Starting from this point**, the key issue is
461 linked to the second objective of this article: to explain the theoretical meaning as well as the analytical consequences of
462 this result for ecology, evolutionary biology, biogeography and biological conservation.

463 The level of coexistence (mean number of concurrent species per macrostate $-\mu S_M-$ within a given antinode, see
464 Fig. 1) decreases with the increase of $\sigma_{Ee} \cdot \sigma_{Hp}$ ($r = -0.8219$, $p = 0.00003$; Fig. 3a) above the threshold value of $0.5 \cdot \hbar_e^{ec}$.
465 This result indicates that an increasing degree of ecological compaction (c_e) in the performance of ecological niche (a
466 higher value of $\sigma_{Ee} \cdot \sigma_{Hp}$ with a smaller mean distance inter-nodes) is not in favor of species coexistence at the intra-
467 survey level. Obviously, this is an important point in favor of CEP. At the same time, as the “distance” between $0.5 \cdot \hbar_e^{ec}$
468 and a given value of $\sigma_{Ee} \cdot \sigma_{Hp} > 0.5 \cdot \hbar_e^{ec}$ increases with the progression of the regression line from left to right in Fig. 3a,
469 then the remaining elements of the species set per macrostate (whose number is smaller and smaller with the increase of
470 $\sigma_{Ee} \cdot \sigma_{Hp}$) are more and more tolerant to the degree of compaction in the performance of ecological niche. This result
471 requires additional clarifications (following paragraphs).

472 According to Fig. 3a, 3b, and Eq. (17); the association between S and H_T , studied through the functional influence of
473 $\sigma_{Ee} \cdot \sigma_{Hp}$, can be divided in three functional stretches:

474 **Stretch (1)**: from $S = 0$ to $S = S_c$ at $\sigma_{Hp} \cdot \sigma_{Ee} = 0.5 \cdot \hbar_e^{ec}$ (see point l_1 in Fig. 3a and l_1' in Fig. 3b). According to Eq. (14)
475 and Fig. 2d, the border value (l_1) between this first stretch and the following one is unreachable from above (i.e., from
476 stretch 2, see below) under natural conditions due to factors that mainly depend on environmental influences (i.e.,
477 species diversity and energy supply linked to each other by means of quantum ecological uncertainty: $\sigma_{Hp} \cdot \sigma_{Ee}$). This
478 stretch involves two corollaries that are evident by themselves: **(1a)**: the ultra-strong alternative of the classical
479 statement of CEP, which was assumed above as an analytical step, is a chimera. That is to say, there are no natural
480 coexistence conditions in which two ecological niches could be totally different to each other; a given degree of
481 ecological overlap in terms of interspecific interference on intraspecific relationships in regard to niche performance is
482 unavoidable. **(1b)**: As a consequence of 1a, there is a high degree of functional contingency in regard to niche
483 performance. That is to say, the width and shape of any ecological niche under universal ecological conditions in which
484 $\sigma_{Ee} \cdot \sigma_{Hp} \gg 0.5 \cdot \hbar_e^{ec}$ undergoes constant fluctuations (i.e., inter- σ_i oscillations, see previous comments in regard to Fig. 1,
485 Section 2.1) depending on the total set of concurrent niches. Such fluctuations prevent that any ecological niche can be
486 exclusively and purely performed depending on intraspecific relationships ruled by the particular genetic heritage of
487 species. As a result, intraspecific relationships result more and more disturbed by the influences of interspecific
488 relationships, in an increased measure with the increase of H_T values. This increasing degree of disturbance blurs the
489 classical limits between concurrent niches, producing a seeming higher redundancy level (in reality: quantum ecological
490 uncertainty, see below).

491 **Stretch (2):** from l_i (where $S = S_c$ at $\sigma_{E_e} \cdot \sigma_{H_p} = 0.5 \cdot \hbar_e^{ec}$) to l_s (where it is reached an ecological saturation level in
492 which $S_u \rightarrow S_T$ and $S_u\% \rightarrow 100\%$) at a very high limit value of species diversity in which $H_{Tmax} \approx 5.640$ nat/individuals
493 (see Eq. (17) and Fig. 3b). Throughout this stretch, there is an increasing ecological uncertainty and functional
494 *complementarity*, either from the ecological point of view (i.e., functional linkage between different species in order to
495 perform a given ecological function in a more efficient way) or from the physical point of view (i.e., relationship
496 between variables Θ_e and Ω_e –see Eq. (14)– that are complementary to each other due to a trade-off between σ_{Θ_e} and
497 σ_{Ω_e} ; see Fig. 2c). Both kinds of complementarities are equivalent to each other in this analytical framework. Within this
498 stretch, neither complete differentiation nor complete equivalence between niches is coherent with reality. The
499 overwhelming majority of living creatures on the planet surface lives at a certain point within this stretch under steady
500 natural conditions. This stretch includes two additional corollaries closely connected to the main goal of this article
501 **(2a):** According to Figs. 2a–2e and corollaries (1a) and (1b), it is impossible, even in principle in addition to in practice,
502 to define the ecological niche of a given species in a way as accurate as we want due to an objective limit given by
503 $0.5 \cdot \hbar_e^{ec}$. **(2b):** According to Eq. (17) and Fig. 3b, the objective space of ecological uncertainty between l_i and l_s per
504 taxocenosis significantly increases with H_T . In addition, given that any ecosystem of high species diversity acts as a sort
505 of “warehouse of species” including several tens or even hundreds of taxocenes, then it is perfectly expectable that our
506 degree of uncertainty in regard to the assessment of ecological niche increases with H_T . This explains the supposed
507 “high degree of FR” allegedly detected in those ecosystems of high H_T values. That is to say, if the accuracy with which
508 we are able to assess any ecological niche is limited by quantum reasons (Section 4.2 analyzes the exact cause at the
509 small scale as well as the eco-evolutionary meaning of this fact), then the foregone reaction in the understanding of
510 species coexistence is to assume “redundancy” (perfect equivalence between niches) when in fact the correct term
511 should be “uncertainty” (see Rodríguez et al., 2013b, pp. 10-11); that is to say: impossibility of describing the
512 ecological niche with accuracy enough as to assert if two or even more species are performing perfectly equivalent
513 ecological functions, or not.

514 **Stretch (3):** This stretch is more a point (or a transition zone) at a metastable level of ecological oversaturation ($l_o >$
515 l_s), than a truly stable ecological state. This zone is a “photographic negative” of stretch (1). That is to say, if the first
516 stretch is characterized by an unattainable null influence of interspecific relationships on intraspecific relationships in
517 regard to niche performance, and the second one is characterized by a progressive overlap between these two type of
518 relationships progressively biased in favor of interspecific links; the third stretch is characterized by the overwhelming
519 influence of interspecific relationships on intraspecific relationships in regard to niche performance. In general, this
520 unbalance can have dramatic consequences either from the ecological or evolutionary point of view due to the cyclical
521 influence of biotic environmental opportunities for the successful deployment of new options of genetic innovation
522 (their most general traits are explored in the following section). This zone is a sort of ultimate tolerance test for
523 coexistence conditions for every one of the concurrent species. The nature of this definitive test for tolerance to species
524 coexistence depends on answering a key question: How it is possible that $l_o > l_s$? That is to say, if at the ecological
525 saturation level (l_s) it is fulfilled that $S_u \rightarrow S_T$ and $S_u\% \rightarrow 100\%$, then it seems to be absurd that $l_o > l_s$ because this
526 would require an expected total number of species higher than the observed (actual) total number of species (S_T) per
527 survey. That is to say, ecological oversaturation ($l_o > l_s$) would be unattainable from the classical point of view due to
528 the following reason: the classical concept of ecological niche is based on a complete coincidence between the
529 functional borders of a given ecological niche, and the genetic borders of a given population according to a particular
530 set of hybridization barriers. Within this framework, it is impossible that $S_u\% > 100\%$. Clarifying this point requires a

531 theoretical parenthesis within our exposition in order to analyze some controversial traits of the classical concept of
532 ecological niche.

533 1) According to Rodríguez et al. (2013b) our current concept of ecological niche depends on the concept of
534 population (see Chase and Leibold, 2003). In other words, the conventional niche concept is a genetically
535 delimited statistical unit with reference to a given number of individuals belonging to a particular species that is
536 isolated by means of hybridization barriers into a given space and time. This concept has no sense below the
537 population level because not even two individuals belonging to the same species are perfectly identical to each
538 other (see Violle et al., 2012) in spite of their capability of genetic exchange with reproductive goals. They only
539 share certain wide-ranging similarity that would be harder to attain in the same measure in which $I_e \rightarrow 0$, because
540 in this circumstance each individual would be a singular and unrepeatable ecological entity. I.e., I_e (Eq. (5)) = 0 if
541 and only if $n_i = 1$ for all the species included in the calculation of H_T (see Eq. (1)); and under these circumstances
542 $S_u\% \approx 100\%$ and $H_T \rightarrow 6.00$ according to Eq. (17). This circumstance is very close to what happens in tropical
543 forests, where at least 1000 trees must be sampled before species richness can be compared among sites (Palmer et
544 al., 2000). These traits envisage two options that are complementary to each other: **(3.1.a)** The classical niche
545 concept loses the most of its meaning for ecosystems of very high species diversity because the number of very
546 similar individuals belonging to a given species is lower and lower due to the increasing degree of ecological
547 patchiness across a wide range of scales (see, e.g., Kaspari et al., 2011; Grünbaum, 2012; Kamakura et al., 2015)
548 in the same sense in which diversity is higher. **(3.1.b)** We, in general, tend to neglect the fractal nature of the
549 concept (i.e., it would be possible to speak about ecosystem niches, taxocene's niches, guild's niches, the
550 conventional niche at the species level, and even about individual's micro-niches) as well as the subordination of
551 genetic elements to environmental elements in the ecological realm. E.g., a tadpole, a water-worm, or a caterpillar
552 remain included in different samples and they have different ecological functions with regard to its frog, its
553 mosquito and its butterfly, respectively, independently that each couple's member belongs to the same species.
554 This happens because ecologists, strictly speaking, are more interested in the functional interpretation than in the
555 taxonomic description of communities. That is to say, despite our bias in favor of genetics when we establish an
556 equivalence population \leftrightarrow species \leftrightarrow niche, we need to be aware that the only way in which an egg is able to
557 know that it contains a well-fitted genetic load is to become a lizard or a bird, since these ecological states decide
558 the viability of the egg's genetic content. Consequently, there have been an all-encompassing underlying dilemma
559 in ecology which has had an undervalued influence on the development of conventional ecological thought: **1**
560 ecological niche \equiv **1** population \equiv the local expression of **1** species genetically isolated by hybridization barriers; is
561 this a truly fruitful methodological assumption for ecological analysis, or not?

562 2) As a result of item (3.1), it is very hard to accept that the classical concept of ecological niche is as valid for the
563 case shown in Fig. 4a as for the case shown in Fig. 4b, despite both cases refer to two taxocenes with the same k_e
564 and h_e^{ec} values. The wider and less compacted structure of the whole set of ecological niches in Fig. 4a allows a
565 more exact understanding of ecological dynamics by using the classical concept of ecological niche than in the
566 case of Fig. 4b. That is to say, the set of packets of intraspecific connections of every species in Fig. 4b is more
567 compacted and pushed on itself by the set of interspecific connections than in Fig. 4a. Individuals are neither
568 physiological nor ethological inert in front of this change of conditions, despite the constancy of their genetic
569 heritage at the species level.

570 3) From items (3.1) and (3.2), in combination with the meaning of stretch (1), it is evident that the classical concept
571 of ecological niche is only valid for “virgin” species of very recent evolution placed in an eco-evolutionary
572 position as close as possible to the points l_i and l_i' in Fig. 3. That is to say, species poorly engaged in a strong web
573 of interspecific relationships. Every additional step toward l_o in Fig. 3b means a progressive distancing from an
574 ecological niche constrained by genotypic factors and performed at the population level, to an ecological niche
575 performed at other scales (a guild, a small group of individuals, or even a single individual) and constrained by
576 environmental factors.

577

578 The items above mean that it is possible that $l_o > l_i$, because under oversaturated ecological conditions the real
579 functional ecological unit works either above or below the species level. This is a sort of “biological rehearsal” of the
580 evolutionary emergence of *Homo sapiens*: if we equate the meaning of the diversity of ecological niches in natural
581 ecosystems with the meaning of the diversity of productive socio-economic functions in society (see, among many
582 others: Clark et al., 1964; Marcuzzi and Camuffo, 1968; Hackbart and Anderson, 1975; Odum, 2007; Margalef, 1991, p.
583 870; Matutinović, 2001) then we are able to grasp that we belong to the only species that has completely broken the
584 boundaries imposed by the CEP (i.e.: in nature, below l_i , one species ↔ one ecological niche; but in society one human
585 species ↔ a potentially unlimited number of socio-economic functions). This is the most important eco-evolutionary
586 event that characterizes the current geological period a.k.a “Anthropocene” (see Zalasiewicz et al., 2011).

587 Fig. 5 is a semi-quantitative diagram of the variety of positions and options in regard to the spectrum of interspecific
588 relationships along the sequence of the above-commented stretches, by using Fig. 3b as a general framework of
589 reference. According to the criteria applied by Rodríguez et al. (2013b) in order to understand interspecific relationships
590 in terms of coupled oscillations between ecological assemblages (A_e : taxocenosis, guild, species, individual, etc.), it is
591 possible to identify the following options (see Fig. 5): **(0)**: complete functional independence in regard to ecological
592 niche performance between both A_e s; diversity and energy oscillations are completely independent to each other;
593 absence of quantum ecological uncertainty. **(1)**: *Neutralism*: species coexist in the large scale within the ecosystem
594 without direct mutual influences. **(2)**: *Amensalism*: an element (black dot and black oscillations) constrains the
595 development of another element (smaller gray dot and smaller gray oscillations) without any costs or benefits received
596 by the other one. **(3)**: *Interspecific competition*: $\approx 180^\circ$ out of phase between both oscillations, i.e., every maximum or
597 minimum coincides with the opposite phase (either a minimum or a maximum, respectively) of the complementary
598 oscillation. This situation does not produce an instantaneous extinction (destructive wave interference because crests
599 and troughs cancel each other out) because both populations are not equal to each other in number of individuals; i.e.:
600 gray dot > black dot at the population level, although gray dot < black dot if the mean size per individual would be
601 considered. **(4)**: *Predation*: a smaller group of predators (black oscillation and black dot, smaller than the gray ones)
602 feeds on a larger group of preys (gray oscillation and gray dot); $\approx 90^\circ$ out of phase between both population oscillations,
603 i.e., every maximum or minimum of the wave amplitude coincides with a node (change of phase) of the complementary
604 oscillation. *Parasitism* would be similar to **(4)**, but in the other way around in regard to population abundance and
605 individual size. **(5)**: *Protocooperation and mutualism*: $\approx 0^\circ$ out of phase between both oscillations, i.e., every maximum
606 or minimum coincides with the same phase (either a maximum or a minimum, respectively) of the complementary
607 oscillation. In *protocooperation* (a not obligatory interaction in which both interacting populations benefit from each
608 other without an intimate anatomical connection) the mean values of both populations in the H_p, E_e scalar space do not
609 coincide with each other either in position or in size (as in this figure). *Mutualism* (an obligatory alternative of

610 *protocooperation*) is equivalent to option 5 but, in addition, both wave amplitudes coincide to each other and there is
611 only one mean value for both populations, or two mean values that coincide in position but not in size (i.e., the H_p , E_e
612 point is the same, but in general a population is more abundant than the other one). These +, + interspecific
613 relationships do not produce an instantaneous population blowup due to inter-population resonance (i.e., a constructive
614 interference from the physical point of view, or a sort of “*explosion of life*”, according to Watkinson, 2003) that would
615 be the opposite case to item (3) providing they are being constrained by the “ecological noise” (Mao et al., 2003)
616 produced by the background of interspecific relationships between the remaining species. Empirical examples that
617 support this micro-models of interspecific relationships are included below (Fig. 9, Section 4.3.1) by using data of
618 species pairs from survey “cor”.

619 In summary, this section shows that the performance of ecological niche is statistically composed by three eco-
620 evolutionary domains in function of H_T values (Fig. 3b) at the intra-taxocenosis level: (1) from $S = 0$ to l_t (intraspecific
621 scale of the ecological niche that mainly depends on *genetic elements*); (2) from l_t to l_s (interspecific scale of the
622 ecological niche that mainly depends on *ecological elements* due to the functional hookup of the set of species as a
623 whole); (3) from l_s to l_o (metastable domain or oversaturated transition area, in which the genetic elements of the first
624 domain, as well as the environmental elements of the second one, are subordinated to *evolutionary elements* whose
625 meaning is explained in the following section of this article).

626

627 4.2 The small-scale explanation of quantum ecological uncertainty and the general environmental scenario 628 in favor of macroevolutionary jumps

629 The central question to be answered in this section is: What is the effect of the connection between efficiency of
630 energy consumption and quantum ecological uncertainty on the ecological success of genetic innovations in order to
631 promote macroevolutionary changes?

632 Conventional FR implies that the elements of a species group drifts toward a given point in a multi-dimensional
633 space of resources (a.k.a.: n -dimensional hypervolume; see Hutchinson, 1957), by sharing similar average values (μ)
634 and oscillations (σ) in regard to a given set of ecological indicators. The direct and one-dimensional scalar comparison
635 of such an ecological drift between H_p and E_e is unfeasible since both variables are expressed in different units (H_p :
636 nat/individual; E_e : eco-Joule, see Section 2.1). Nevertheless, the coefficient of variation ($CV = \sigma/\mu$, or $(\sigma/\mu) \times 100$) is
637 dimensionless and scale invariant, allowing dependable comparisons between variables expressed in different units.
638 Figs. 6a and 6b show that there is a convergence between CV_{H_p} and CV_{E_e} either in regard to the spectrum of overtones
639 (o_n , see Fig. 1) or in regard to the increase of quantum ecological redundancy ($\sigma_{E_e} \cdot \sigma_{H_p}$) across the spectrum of overtones
640 per survey. The mutual ratios between CV_{H_p} and CV_{E_e} also converge to 1 across the spectrum of $\sigma_{E_e} \cdot \sigma_{H_p}$ values (Fig.
641 6c). These results seem to be in agreement with the conventional hypothesis of complete FR. However, is this
642 convergence of coefficients of variation equivalent to a drift toward a same point into the H_p , E_e scalar field with the
643 ecosystem oscillations? There are three noticeable trends from Fig. 6d (o_1) to 6f (o_{16}) in order to respond this
644 question:

- 645 1) Voronoi lines change from a vertical to a diagonal direction. So ecological niches are preferably partitioned
646 along the abscissas (\leftrightarrow ; i.e., in function of H_p values) at the level of low overtones (Fig. 6d), but they are
647 preferably partitioned along the ordinates (\updownarrow ; i.e., in function of E_e values) at high overtones (Fig. 6f).

- 648 2) In a coincidence with the results reflected by Figs. 6a to 6c; CV_{H_p} decreases along the abscissas from Fig. 6d to
649 6f (66.67%, 53.99%, and 47.44%, respectively) in approximately the same fashion in which CV_{E_e} increases
650 along the ordinates (13.34%, 39.41%, and 93.40%, respectively). This means that when the spectrum of H_p
651 values is more and more homogeneously partitioned to accommodate more macrostates, the set of mean eco-
652 kinetic energy values per individual per macrostate results more and more stacked on each other in agreement
653 with the expected pattern starting from the conventional CEP's statement. As a result, it is impossible that two
654 elements within the ecosystem can converge toward a same functional point even in the simplest case of a
655 scalar field of two dimensions, providing that this field is influenced by quantum ecological uncertainty. In even
656 simpler words: if the combination of ecological niches at the macrostate level are too partitioned along the
657 abscissas (i.e., compressed within their respective antinodes due to the reduction of λ_e –reduction of the distance
658 inter-nodes– with the increase of overtone number), it results expanded in the same fashion along the ordinates,
659 and vice versa. Figs. 6g, 6h, and 6i show that the same pattern shown by Figs. 6d–6f in regard to macrostates is
660 also valid at the species level, even with regard to macrostates of maximum E_{eTp} values (see Eq. (4)) in which
661 competition intensity should be lower precisely because of the higher amount of total available energy.
662 Consequently, *the essential explanation of quantum ecological uncertainty at the small scale* is the following: it
663 is statistically impossible to keep any kind of living unit (either a species or an individual) embedded in a given
664 ecological assemblage (ecosystem, taxocene, guild, macrostate, etc.) trapped in a potential well of H_p , E_e (see
665 the concepts of B-D_{TO-H}, thermo-statistical accretion center and ecological cavity resonator in Section 2.1) able
666 to simultaneously reduce, or expand, both variables with the same intensity and direction. The ecosystem
667 constantly fluctuates across its spectrum of overtones in order to simultaneously retaining, consuming and
668 distributing energy to all of the living creatures (see explanations in the comment in regard to Fig. 1, Section
669 2.1). Consequently, if the H_p , E_e realized scalar field of any ecological assemblage is more compressed and
670 partitioned along the abscissas, then it results more expanded and less partitioned along the ordinates; and if it is
671 depressed and more partitioned along the ordinates, then it results more expanded and less partitioned along the
672 abscissas. As a result, the opposite correlation between σ_{H_p} and σ_{E_e} implies that when the level of interspecific
673 coexistence *increases* (FR) on the abscissas (i.e., lower σ_{H_p} values) the level of interspecific coexistence
674 *decreases* (CEP) on the ordinates (i.e., higher σ_{E_e} values), and vice versa. This explains why FR and CEP are
675 inextricably connected with each other as two sides of the same coin.
- 676 3) At the maximum overtone number (o_16 , Fig. 6f) there is a macrostate (M_d) that reaches an energy level
677 noticeably higher than the rest of the energy levels per macrostate within this overtone. This anomalous
678 behavior cannot be explained by an increase of eco-kinetic energy or “ecological temperature” at the large
679 scale, since the ecosystem as a whole is under stationary ecological conditions. That is to say, there is an input-
680 output balance in regard to energy exchange with the outside. As a result, H_T ; $m_{e(\mu)}$; $m_{eTs(\mu)}$; $I_{e(\mu)}$; E_{eT} ; $E_{eTp(\mu)}$;
681 $E_{e(\mu)}$; $S_e = N_{Ts} \cdot H_T$ (where m_{eTs} : total biomass per survey, N_{Ts} : total number of individuals per survey, and S_e :
682 entropy); P_e ; V_e ; etc., remain constant with time. Therefore, there is only one explanation of maximum
683 plausibility: M_d is being “pushed” toward a very high eco-kinetic energy level (≈ 5 times higher than the mean
684 energy level of the rest of the macrostates) by the combined interspecific pressure from the remaining set of
685 macrostates across the spectrum of H_p values, until reaching the ecological equivalent of a degenerate state of
686 matter in physics. Degenerate matter is a quantum state in which a large fraction of the pressure is due to the
687 fulfillment of the Pauli exclusion principle (i.e.: two identical fermions –in general, particles with half-integer

688 spin, like electrons, protons, neutrinos, quarks, and neutrons— cannot occupy the same quantum state
689 simultaneously). That is to say, under quotidian physical conditions a noticeable increase of pressure is due to
690 two main influences: either by a decrease of volume under a constant temperature, or by an increase of
691 temperature under a constant volume (Boyle-Mariotte’s law; see Eq. (9) in the physical case and Eq. (8) in the
692 ecological case). But, when a given amount of plasma is compressed and cooled (from the equivalence between
693 Eq. (8) and Eq. (9): ecological succession = ecological cooling; see additional comments below), there is a limit
694 in which the Pauli exclusion principle begins to act and there is not extra space for any particle. Thus, according
695 to Eq. (13) and taken *position* (x) and *momentum* (p) as complementary variables, σ_x is extremely low (i.e., a
696 given set of particles is confined in a very small local space), meanwhile σ_p is extremely high due to the trade-
697 off between σ_x and σ_p (quantum uncertainty principle in physics). So, even if the plasma is very cold, some
698 particles must be moving very fast (with great kinetic energy) in order to avoid sharing the same quantum states
699 of the remaining fermions in agreement with the Pauli Exclusion Principle statement. This means that a larger
700 and larger fraction of P in Eq. (9) depends on the Pauli Exclusion Principle rather than on the temperature.
701 According to theoretical arguments and empirical analysis provided by Rodríguez et al. (2013b), ecological
702 succession is equivalent to a cooling process in which more and more species are compacted within a same
703 space starting from a constant input of available energy at the large scale (solar constant = 1.361 kW/m²) in
704 order to reach higher and higher information amounts (H_T) at lower and lower I_e and λ_e values (see Rodríguez et
705 al., 2015c, Fig. 5c). But, obviously, this process of ecological compaction of species has an insurmountable
706 limit under constant k_e and h_e^{ec} values due to a combination of quantum ecological uncertainty + CEP that is
707 ecologically equivalent to a combination of quantum uncertainty in physics + Pauli exclusion principle,
708 respectively. As a result, degenerate ecological states (like M_d in Fig. 6f) emerge, mainly at high overtone
709 numbers and under high H_T values, in order to avoid sharing the same ecological positions of the remaining
710 internal ecological assemblages of the system, in agreement with the classical statement of CEP. That is to say,
711 an ecological system is cooler and more compacted in the same measure in which H_T is higher. When the
712 system oscillates at high overtones under these conditions, a larger and larger fraction of $P_{e(s)}$ in Eq. (8) depends
713 on the CEP (the ecological equivalent of Pauli exclusion principle) rather than on the total amount of the
714 system’s internal energy. There are certain conditions (they will be analyzed in Section 4.3.2) that facilitate the
715 emergence of degenerate ecological states and may stimulate the evolutionary yield of genetic variations. But
716 the important factor at this point is to highlight that the set of energy peaks associated to the emergence of
717 degenerate ecological states simply arises, at least up to a point, as a direct outcome from the random partition
718 of a gradient of species diversity by means of competition nodes throughout a spectrum of overtones (i.e., from
719 Fig. 1d1 to 1d2, and from Fig. 1e1 to 1e2). This produces an increasing pressure from the background of
720 interspecific relationships on the abscissas in the same measure in which the resulting antinodes are narrower
721 and narrower. The resulting pressure is relieved when some macrostates are “pushed” toward significantly
722 higher energy levels on the ordinates = emergence of degenerate ecological states.

723

724 If the above-mentioned mechanism of emergence of degenerate ecological states is coherent with the real ecological
725 dynamics, then it should be possible to see that a process of H_T increase under constant k_e and h_e^{ec} values produces a
726 more conspicuous emergence of highly degenerated ecological states at high overtone numbers (in a similar fashion to
727 M_d in Fig. 6f), even if the total amount of eco-kinetic energy per survey (E_{eTs}) decreases. Fig. 7a shows the analysis of

728 extremes performed on E_e values per macrostates of high overtones of three surveys under stationary ecological
729 conditions by using Statistica-6 (StatSoft Inc., 2001). These values were taken as probable degenerate ecological states
730 per overtone. From Fig. 7b to 7d, it is possible to see that the number of degenerate ecological states as well as their
731 magnitude (assessed as $\mu E_{e,Md}/\mu E_{eM}$; where $\mu E_{e,Md}$: mean value of eco-kinetic energy per individual per degenerate or
732 highly degenerate $-\mu E_{e,Md(h)}$ macrostate, and μE_{eM} : general mean value of E_e at the overtone level) increases with the
733 overtone number (18 \rightarrow 19 \rightarrow 22) as well as with the increase of total species diversity (H_T : 1.71 \rightarrow 1.28 \rightarrow 2.41)
734 despite the decreasing value of total eco-kinetic energy per survey (E_{eTs} : 1.79E+5 \rightarrow 1.75E+5 \rightarrow 4.14E+4). That is to
735 say, in the same measure in which the possible spectrum of H_p values is filled in the abscissas, the spectrum of E_e values
736 is pushed to higher and higher levels in the ordinates due to the decreasing value of “ecological temperature” (i.e.,
737 increase of ecological compaction with H_T), and despite the reduction of total energy.

738 An ecologically dominant species can be present across the whole possible spectrum of macrostates and overtones in
739 a given survey (e.g., see species Cn and Mc in Fig. 9c). Taking this into account, and in agreement with our previous
740 analysis of the concept of ecological niche (see items 1, 2 and 3 in regard to stretch 3, Section 4.1), it is difficult to
741 accept that two individuals of a same species i can be included into a same ecological niche if one of them is living in a
742 macrostate with 7.28 fold more energy than the other one (e.g., Fig. 7d). This result supports that the exclusively genetic
743 criterion usually applied in order to define the concept of ecological niche (1 ecological niche \equiv 1 population \equiv 1
744 species) has important drawbacks, mainly when the functional spectrum of species is significantly wide under
745 conditions of large mean body size and high species diversity values. In these cases the conventional species concept
746 should be replaced by the concept of epigenetic species (see Rasnitsyn, 2007): a group of organism that, despite the
747 nature and degree of their reproductive isolation from other concurrent organism, are performing a similar or associated
748 ecological function that depends on similar coordinates within the H_p , E_e scalar field.

749 Due to the fulfillment of quantum uncertainty principle and Pauli exclusion principle in quantum mechanics, a
750 particle in a very cold and dense highly degenerate state is paradoxically similar to a molecule of very hot water vapor
751 in comparison with liquid water in statistical mechanics: both particles are in a sort of free non-interacting state in
752 regard to the remaining particles due to the noticeable difference of energy levels between the particle and its large-
753 scale physical background. Thus, following with the development of this proposal in ecology, every degenerate
754 ecological state (M_d in Figs. 6f and 7) should be regarded as a state of weakened interaction with the general
755 background of interspecific relationships within the ecosystem: a sort of *ecological isolation that does not depend on*
756 *the influence of geographic isolation*, which is an essential element in the Darwinian theory of evolution. In other
757 words, a high degree of species coexistence tends to push small species groups toward degenerate ecological states
758 functionally isolated from their ecological background, *even under sympatric conditions*.

759 So species coexistence *per se* must be regarded as a key evolutionary force (e.g., the Red Queen hypothesis: any
760 element within an evolutionary system is forced to evolve just in order to maintain its level of adjustment regarding the
761 remaining elements of the system, or it is necessary running very strong only to keep the same relative position within
762 the respective adaptive zone; see van Valen, 1973; Dawkins and Krebs, 1979; Benton, 2009; Liow et al., 2011), mainly
763 due to the quantum nature of ecosystem dynamics. That is to say, species could be eco- evolutionarily running in the
764 short run, just to gain ecological momentum ($p_e = m_e \times I_e$; see Eq. (10)) in order to perform large evolutionary leaps in
765 the long run. For example, Rabosky and Adams (2012a) have reported that rates of morphological evolution are
766 correlated with species richness in salamanders. According to these authors, this coupling between species
767 diversification and phenotypic evolution is consistent with the hypothesis that clades with high rates of morphological

768 trait evolution may diversify more than clades with low rates, so underlying processes of diversity regulation (as the
769 emergence of degenerate ecological states) have important consequences for interpreting macroevolutionary patterns.

770 In previous comments it has been explained that +, + interspecific relationships (i.e. protocoperation and
771 mutualism, see pattern 5 in Fig. 5) do not produce an instantaneous population blowup due to inter-population
772 resonance, providing that any pair of species engaged in these relationships is constrained by the ecological noise from
773 the background of interspecific relationships at the ecosystem level. However, if mutualism and degenerate ecological
774 states are combined with each other within a highly compacted ecological assemblage (e.g., at l_o in Fig. 3b; see also
775 comments in regard to stretch 3 in Section 4.1), then this is the general environmental scenario (i.e.: advantageous
776 ecological association between a selected species local group + local energy maximum in comparison with the
777 ecological background + local weakening of ecological constrictions because of functional isolation from the
778 surrounding ecological noise) in favor of a discontinuous macroevolutionary jump between two consecutive ecological
779 states with different k_e and h_e^{ec} values. In fact, recent evidence reveals that parasites as well as non-mutualist taxa are
780 nested within ancestrally mutualistic clades (Sachs and Simms, 2006). Obviously, two additional conditions are needed:
781 the appropriate set of genetic mutations + a free functional ecological space (potential niche) vacant for suitably
782 receiving the recently evolved biological entity (ecological opportunity hypothesis, see Mahler et al., 2010; Schweizer
783 et al., 2014). Thus, the most probable option is that a typical rainforest is an ecosystem without any surrounding free
784 adaptive zone to expel the evolutionary product of its highly degenerate internal macrostates. Or, putting it into
785 perspective, rainforest ecosystems produced their most advanced macroevolutionary sprout ≈ 71 –63 million years ago
786 (i.e., the primitive ancestors of current primates; see Springer et al., 2012). With the resulting effect, in the long run, that
787 human civilization itself is the most modern evolutionary product from rainforest ecosystems.

788 Macroevolutionary jumps are ecologically equivalent to instantaneous electronic transitions by means of quantum
789 jumps (Schrödinger, 1952; Itano et al., 2014) between different energy levels in physics. For a pair of evolutionarily
790 contiguous taxocenosis t_{x1} and t_{x2} belonging to different eco-physical scales it is fulfilled that $k_e = 1.3806504E\phi$
791 $J_e \cdot \text{nat}/\text{individual}$ and $h_e^{ec} = 6.62606957E\phi J_e \cdot \text{nat}/\text{individual}$. Hence, a successful macroevolutionary leap from t_{x1} to t_{x2}
792 must imply a given level of degeneration supported by an energy gradient in comparison with the mean energy level of
793 its ecological background (μE_{eM}) higher than $\mu E_{e,Md}/\mu E_{eM} = 10$ (since $\phi = -x_i, \dots, -3, -2, -1, 0, +1, +2, +3, \dots, +x_i$ in k_e and
794 h_e^{ec}). That is to say, the leap from t_{x1} to t_{x2} must involve an even more degenerate macrostate than $M_{d(th)}$ in Fig 7d (for
795 which $E_{e,Md(th)}/\mu E_{eM} = 7.28$). The degree of interspecific compaction to get $\mu E_{e,Md}/\mu E_{eM} \geq 10$ can only be attained step by
796 step, either by *speciation* or by *microevolution* in order to get a gradual increase of H_T until reaching l_o in Fig. 3b.

797 The above-mentioned sequence of microevolution \rightarrow speciation \rightarrow macroevolution \rightarrow microevolution \rightarrow and so
798 on... means that the eco-evolutionary process as a whole involves a multilayer sequence of compact eco-evolutionary
799 blocks. An eco-evolutionary block is here defined as a given set of species that evolves at or below the species level
800 under similar environmental conditions at the large scale, by keeping constant values of k_e and h_e^{ec} . Each one of these
801 eco-evolutionary blocks, in turn, includes several internal states (i.e., successional positions from conditions
802 characterized by r selection to conditions characterized by K selection) that combine increasing values of H_T and E_e ,
803 ruled by the influence of quantum ecological uncertainty and CEP across the respective spectrum of overtones. This
804 intra-block process raises an appropriate level of species compaction in order to attain a maximum efficiency in the
805 consumption of energy supply, until reaching a high degree of ecological degeneration at the highest overtones.

806 Between two contiguous eco-evolutionary blocks, there is an empty or almost empty adaptive zone because of the
807 discontinuous (discrete) variations of ϕ . This is the space for relatively “instantaneous” macroevolutionary jumps,

808 when an appropriate combination of general environmental scenario + suitable mutations + free functional ecological
809 space for ecesis emerges. Eco-evolutionary movements across this empty space implies a transient successional
810 regression from a high H_T , E_e coordinate in the previous block to an early low value of H_T for the following block that,
811 initially, it is incapable to reach those terminal energy levels that characterize highly degenerate ecological states. This
812 jump involves an ecological translation from a K strategy in the previous block to an initial r strategy in the new one,
813 that is comparatively more K than the previous K itself. The new block, in turn, will evolve again by the above-
814 mentioned ecological way in order to expand a new field of H_p' , E_e values constrained by constant $k_{e,i+1}$ and $h_{e^{ec}}^{ec}$
815 values. When this $i+1$ block is completely full (i.e., maximum partition of the spectrum of H_p' values and maximum
816 stacking of E_e values) it reaches a new highly degenerate ecological state capable to perform a subsequent
817 macroevolutionary jumps from $k_{e,i+1}$ and $h_{e^{ec}}^{ec}$ to $k_{e,i+2}$ and $h_{e^{ec}}^{ec}$, and so on... According to Uyeda et al. (2011), the
818 delay due to the accumulation of bounded microevolutionary changes between two successive macroevolutionary leaps
819 is, in the average, 1 million years.

820 This cyclic process as a whole “absorbs” physical energy from the abiotic environment, fixing it in the form of an
821 increasing mean value of biomass and a decreasing value of dispersal capability (Eq. (5)) per individual with the
822 increment of H_T . The opposite process (eco-evolutionary degradation) goes in the other way around and discharges eco-
823 kinetic energy in form of heat into the abiotic environment, taking it from a decreasing mean biomass and an increasing
824 dispersal per individual with the decrement of H_T . These two opposite trends may be in equilibrium with each other in
825 the short run regarding a given clade or group of clades (e.g., Ricklefs and Jønsson, 2014; Silvestro et al., 2014);
826 although it is clear that the first one of them should prevail in the very long run and at the large scale (i.e.: it is a
827 diversity-dependent non-equilibrium evolutionary process; e.g., Quental and Marshall, 2013) within a biosphere aimed
828 to an energy-dependent net increase of species diversity in order to get a net reduction of internal entropy.

829 Fig. 8 recreates one of the steps across the previously described eco-evolutionary progression by using two
830 contiguous eco-evolutionary blocks (ruderal vegetation –rv, gray color– and Mediterranean shrubland –Ms, black color)
831 based on real values of $\mu_{H_p'}$, $\sigma_{H_p'}$, μ_{E_e} , and σ_{E_e} from equivalent spectra of overtones (from o_1 to o_{14}) for both blocks.
832 Intra-block oscillations indicate trophodynamic fluctuations (in a similar way to Fig. 1) linked to eco-evolutionary
833 processes that have time enough to leave clear footprints on the fossil record, at the same time that all of the possible
834 H_p' , E_e points at the intra-EEB level are occupied and rv’s degenerate ecological states are reached. The dotted arrow
835 that connects both blocks indicates the “instantaneous” macroevolutionary jump of a transitional ecological assemblage
836 ($A_{e,t(r)}$) with a low probability to leave abundant transitional fossil forms.

837 From Eq. (17) and Fig. 3b, every intra-block transition from non-degenerate ecological states to degenerate
838 ecological states means a successional increase from $H_T = 0$ (one initial species) to $H_{Tmax} \approx 5.640$ for every block. Then,
839 there is a key question in this regard: Overall, it is not very likely to find that $H_{Tmax} \approx 5.640$ nat/individual for the most
840 of the current taxocenes, providing they are taxonomically well-delimited. That is to say, everybody knows that, for
841 example, a large sample of plankton can reach a very high value of $H_T > H_{Tmax} = 5.640$ in Fig. 3b. But when we say
842 “plankton” this term includes several eco-evolutionary blocks; in a similar way in which a “coral reef” (another
843 example of a high diversity system) is a complex assemblage of many blocks. It seems to be that rainforest trees are the
844 only current “pure” taxocene able to reach this high H_T level (see some examples in the final sentences of Section 3).

845 The answer to that question depends on two main factors: **(a)** According to Rodríguez et al. (2015c) “*All the*
846 *ecosystems are super-systems that include many subsystems interwoven with each others, each of them with its*
847 *particular quantum vibration mode*” (i.e.: *decoherence* or inequality of λ_e , wave amplitude and wave phase between the

848 internal elements of the ecosystem) Such a connection is expressed, in this case, by the overlap zone of the space of
849 uncertainty between “rv” and “Ms” (see o_w in Fig. 8). This set of connections between contiguous blocks supports the
850 possibility of regulation loops due to wave interference across the set of blocks of the biosphere as a whole. **(b)** The
851 structure of any current taxocene is, very frequently, a pale reflection of its ancient heyday in which it had its
852 opportunity to evolve from $H_T = 0$ to $H_{Tmax} \approx 5.640$. E.g., in a very simplified way: early Ordovician for corals; late
853 Ordovician for bivalves and gastropods; Permian for several other types of mollusks as well as for cockroach-like
854 insects, beetles and true bugs in the terrestrial environment; Devonian for fish; late Carboniferous for arthropods, in
855 general; Jurassic-Cretaceous for reptiles; Quaternary for mammals, and Anthropocene for humans and their bio-social
856 diversification in a varied plethora of socio-economic activities. When a large eco-evolutionary block yields the sprout
857 for a succeeding new block, the first one of them results in a certain way self-constrained by its own evolutionary
858 sprouts (e.g., Sahney et al., 2010; Roopnarine and Angielczyk, 2012) within a more narrow range of H_T values due to
859 the changing environmental conditions imposed by the new block that is performing its respective transition from $H_T =$
860 0 to $H_{Tmax} \approx 5.64$, and so on... This coincides with the absence of a positive association between clade age and species
861 diversity across the eukaryotic tree of life (see Rabosky et al., 2012b). When we align this dynamics by using a chart
862 based on data from current taxocenes, we obtain Fig. 3b. However, this contemporary final result is in reality hiding that
863 a long sequence of different l_t , l_s and l_o values and their respective H_T values from 0 to 5.64 have been cyclically
864 reached many times before across the timeline of the evolutionary history of life, by only changing the respective values
865 of k_e and h_e^{ec} throughout a relay race between clades.

866

867 4.3 ...and some analytical consequences

868 4.3.1 Empirical examples of wave micro-models for interspecific relationships in Fig. 5

869 $\sigma_{H_p'}$ and σ_{E_e} are both quantitative indicators of oscillation amplitudes around mean values in the H_p' , E_e scalar field.
870 So the product $\sigma_{H_p'} \times \sigma_{E_e}$ (i.e., the magnitude of quantum ecological uncertainty) is equivalent to a given area within that
871 scalar field (see, e.g., Fig. 8; both boxes, the gray and the black one, are niche areas at the taxocenosis level for ruderal
872 vegetations –rv– and Mediterranean vegetation –Ms–, respectively). Thus, if we overlay all of the positions that a given
873 ecological assemblage (A_e) is able to fill either across the spectrum of overtones or in regard to a concrete overtone into
874 the H_p' , E_e space, then the area obtained shows the size, shape and structure of the A_e 's niche. This procedure has the
875 advantage that $\sigma_{H_p'} \times \sigma_{E_e}$ can be calculated for any type of A_e and at any hierarchical organization level within the
876 ecosystems. For example, Fig. 9a shows that there is a high and significant direct correlation between $\sigma_{H_p'} \times \sigma_{E_e}$ and the
877 total area of the region in the H_p' , E_e scalar field that is bounded by the cubic spline adjustment curve of E_e in function
878 of H_p' (f), the x -axis, and the vertical lines in which $x_i = H_p',_{min}$ and $x_j = H_p',_{max}$. (i.e., the above-mentioned “region” is
879 the integral of E_e in function of H_p' from $H_p',_{min}$ to $H_p',_{max}$, defined as $\int f(H_p') dH_p'$). This area has been measured as the
880 summation of absolute values of $\int f(H_p') dH_p'$ between successive function roots ($y = 0$), since in this case even those
881 values located below the x -axis (integration negative values) contribute to the shape and size of ecological niche.

882 In a similar way, if two or more of these areas are analyzed in combination with each other, then we are able to
883 glimpse part of the functional role and interspecific relationships in which those A_e s are engaged. For example Fig. 9b
884 shows that, over the background of H_p' , E_e values for the set of species as a whole ($\forall Sp.$) for overtone 14, *Montastraea*
885 *cavernosa* (Mc; a very dominant species that embraces 12.61% of the total number of individual of the survey and it is
886 present in 69.7% of the plots) has affinity by degenerate ecological states, and it performs a significantly wider and

887 lesser specialized niche than *Porites astreoides* (Pa). The oscillations of a given species (e.g., Mc in Fig. 9b) can be
888 wider than those of the system as a whole (in one of the axis, at least) because species coexistence smoothes the overall
889 set of oscillations (i.e., a higher ecological stability supported by decoherence) by means of the balance between crests
890 and troughs of energy values. It is obvious in this figure that Pa is a less dominant species whose maximum E_e value
891 per macrostate is biased toward a level of species diversity higher than the H_p ' mean value. In addition, the maximum
892 value of E_e for Pa is deployed just when Mc and $\forall Sp$ reaches a minimum of eco-kinetic energy. According to Fig. 9a, it
893 is possible that Pa is not isolated in this ecological strategy, because it appears closely associated, in regard to ecological
894 niche size at least, with *Siderastrea radians* (Sr) and *Oculina diffusa* (Od).

895 Collaterally (Fig. 9c), the two most dominant species of the survey, (Mc and *Colpophyllia natans* –Cn–), are
896 mutually engaged in an interspecific relationship that empirically exemplifies the pattern ++ labeled as “5” in Fig. 5
897 (i.e., their minimum and maximum values of E_e coincide with each other at equivalent values of H_p ’). On the contrary,
898 Fig. 9d indicates that, despite de above-mentioned coincidence between Pa and Od in regard to niche size, both species
899 seems to compete with each other; in a similar way to the congeneric species *Diploria clivosa* (Dc) and *D. strigosa* (Ds,
900 see Fig. 9e), since in both species pairs E_e crests of one species coincide with E_e troughs of the other one. These two
901 figures can be regarded as empirical examples of pattern labeled as “3” in Fig. 5. Finally, Fig. 9e is in favor of a
902 relationship of neutralism (similar to pattern “1” in Fig. 5) between Sr and *Montastraea faveolata* (Mfa).

903

904 4.3.2 Association between body size and quantum ecological uncertainty. Meaning for life development in 905 the large scale, as well as for insular ecology

906 On the one hand, according to Rodríguez et al. (2012; 2013a, b; 2015a), body size (considering individual biomass –
907 m_e in Eq. (2) and (3)– as an equivalent of it henceforth) is an important indicator from the point of view of physical
908 approach to eco-evolutionary dynamics exposed in this article. This point coincides with the noticeable role
909 conventionally granted to this indicator in ecology and evolutionary biology (see, e.g.: Brown et al., 2004; Woodward et
910 al., 2005; Olson et al., 2009; DeLong et al., 2015;), in which the increase of body size can be regarded as a general
911 intra– and inter–eco-evolutionary block trend (Cope’s Rule; see MacFadden, 1986; Kingsolver and Pfennig, 2004;
912 Hone et al., 2005). Small-bodied organisms tend to have higher mass-specific metabolic rates in comparison with
913 larger-bodied organisms, either at the intra- or interspecific scale. Thus the increment of body size, despite the apparent
914 delay of evolutionary dynamics that it implies (see below), seems to confer ecological advantages because it is
915 comparatively less expensive in metabolic terms.

916 On the other hand, ecological diversification requires a certain degree of tachygenesis or macroevolutionary
917 acceleration (e.g., Knoll, 1994; Zalasiewicz et al., 2011; Benson and Choiniere, 2013) and species accumulation
918 (Benson et al., 2014; Hedges et al., 2015) in the deep time, in such a way that the increase rate of species number
919 surpasses the natural extinction rate. This cumulative acceleration is slight ($r = -0.2352$ in Fig. 10), but significant ($p =$
920 0.0185), when we indirectly review the evolution of life at the large scale by means of the respective division in
921 chronostratigraphic stages by applying the principle of faunal succession: the same kinds of fauna are found throughout
922 the respective geological layers, following a vertical succession that reflects the evolutionary order (Miall, 2004; Peppe
923 and Deino; 2013). In general, there is a close match between phylogeny and stratigraphy for large clades due to
924 objective and methodological reasons (see Hone et al., 2005, p. 590; as well as Remane et al. 1996, respectively).
925 According to Fig. 10, there has been a reduction of geological stage span of 5000 years ($y = 26.656 - 0.0049 \cdot x$; 1
926 myr-0.0049 \approx 5000) per million years across the last 541 million years. This trend of shortening accelerates to 118000

927 years per million years ($r' = -0.898$, $p = 2E-7$; $y = 541.471 - 0.118 \cdot x$; $1\text{myr} \cdot 0.118 = 118000$ years) if we perform the
928 calculation including only the last 19 stratigraphic stages (starting from the beginning of Ypresian stage) that
929 encompass a total of 56 myr. Firstly, this trend has no definite intrinsic explanation. We can suppose that life needs to
930 wait by certain slow geological events able to promote more favorable environmental conditions. But life itself has been
931 one of the most dynamic geological influences on the planet surface, mainly if we exclude certain astronomical factors
932 with a strong influence at the long run. That is to say, transferring the question from the biological level to the
933 geological one it is somewhat equivalent to pose the same question at a higher level.

934 Secondly, the anti-entropic trend associated with species diversity seems to clash with one of the main conventional
935 conditions of speciation: either complete (in allopatric and peripatric speciation) or partial (in parapatric speciation)
936 geographical isolation. That is to say, there is an association between species diversity and average survival rate per
937 individual because entropy reduction is the only way to accumulate more and more species and biomass starting from
938 an astronomically constrained supply of solar energy. But the addition of more and more species on a limited planetary
939 surface progressively reduces the probability of geographical isolation. As a result, the thermodynamic aim of
940 biological evolution seems to act as a sort of spontaneous self-restriction against one of its main pro-evolutionary
941 genetic requirements. However, this seeming incoherence can be regarded as resolved with the emergence of degenerate
942 ecological states (see Section 4.2 and M_d in Fig. 6 and 7) capable to promote large evolutionary leaps without
943 geographical isolation conditions at all.

944 Thirdly, if there is an association body size \leftrightarrow macroevolutionary rate throughout an evolutionary dynamics
945 influenced by quantum ecological uncertainty, then this association should be presumptively explainable by means of
946 quantum mechanics. This explanation is more valuable in the same measure in which the results about the association
947 between body size and evolutionary rate are contradictory, e.g.: MacFadden (1986: f+); Martin and Palumbi (1993: g-);
948 Cantatore et al. (1994: g+); Nunn and Stanley (1998: g-); Gregory et al. (2000: f+); Kingsolver and Pfennig (2004: f+);
949 Gillooly et al. (2005: g-); Finarelli and Flynn (2006: f+); Fontanillas et al. (2007: g-, 0); Meiri (2008: f-); Adams et al.
950 (2009: f0); Cooper and Purvis (2010: f+, \times); Bromham (2011: g-); Lartillot and Poujol (2011: g-); Evans et al. (2012:
951 f+); Rabosky et al. (2013: f+); Benson et al. (2014: f+); where “g” and “f” means that the authors used either molecular
952 genetics indicators or phenotypic-fossil-paleontological indicators, respectively; and +, -, 0, and \times are reports on direct,
953 opposite, neutral, and complex multidimensional statistical associations between body size and evolutionary rate,
954 respectively. In general: **a**) There seems to be an underlying pattern within this divergent set of conclusions: when
955 genetics indicators are used, there is a trend to obtain opposite associations body size \leftrightarrow evolutionary rate; meanwhile
956 when phenotypic-fossil-paleontological indicators are used, there is a trend to obtain direct associations body size \leftrightarrow
957 evolutionary rate (g+: 1 case; g-: 6 cases; f+: 8 cases; f-: 2 cases; $\chi^2 = 7.14$, $p = 0.0076$). **b**) According to this result, it
958 is possible that the importance of ecological context (stretch 2 in Section 4.1), has been systematically undervalued
959 from the evolutionary point of view, with the resulting overvaluing of intrinsic genetic factors (stretch 1 in Section 4.1).
960 This section is essentially aimed to item **(b)**.

961 It has been established in Section 4.2 that the emergence of degenerate ecological states is “a direct outcome from
962 the random partition of a gradient of species diversity by means of competition nodes throughout a spectrum of
963 overtones (...). This produces an increasing pressure from the background of interspecific relationships on the
964 abscissas in the same measure in which the resulting antinodes are narrower and narrower. The resulting pressure is
965 relieved when some macrostates are “pushed” toward significantly higher energy levels on the ordinates = emergence
966 of degenerate ecological states” So, given Eq. (4) and the successional sacrifice of I_e in order to get higher mean values

967 of biomass per individual (m_e), our understanding of the connection body size \leftrightarrow evolutionary rate requires
 968 understanding the link between m_e and the words “partition” and “pushed” in the previous statement. This connection
 969 depends on the relationship between body size (m_e) and stacking coefficient (C_s), calculated as:

$$970 \quad C_s = \sigma_{E_e} / \sigma_{H_p} \quad (18)$$

971 Eq. (18) means that sustaining a taller and more scattered column (high σ_{E_e} value) of macrostates (set of niches) on a
 972 relatively narrow base of species diversity values (low σ_{H_p} value) indicates a higher performance in regard to the
 973 exploitation of environmental resources (i.e., a “taller” ecological assemblage in the H_p , E_e scalar field). In other words,
 974 those eco-evolutionary blocks with a higher value of h_e^{ec} (the minimum unit of exchange of information by eco-kinetic
 975 energy) have a more efficient performance because they have a higher rate of conversion of competitive pressure
 976 (partition of the H_p gradient) in energy gain. The process of ecological stacking is a product of the combination of CEP
 977 + quantum ecological uncertainty, therefore, it explains why there is a transition zone (between $o_t = 1$ and $o_t \gg 1$) in
 978 the spectrum of statistical distributions of H_p values in which the observed value of h_e^{ec} does not coincide with the
 979 expected one (see Rodríguez et al., 2015c; they mistakenly explained this phenomenon as an statistical limitation of
 980 their model itself): given that CEP and quantum ecological uncertainty are indissolubly linked to the quantum nature of
 981 ecosystems, h_e^{ec} emerges only when the partition of H_p gradient is strong enough to produce a degree of ecological
 982 stacking along the ordinates in the H_p , E_e scalar field, leaving empty spaces between H_p 's categories. Hence ecological
 983 stacking transforms classical continuous statistical distributions of H_p values in discontinuous (quantum) statistical
 984 distributions in which $m_{eM} \times I_{eM} \times \lambda_{eM} = h_e^{ec}$. Besides, given that C_s increases with body size (see following paragraphs),
 985 the capability to hoard the total of available energy was low for small-bodied organism in the evolutionary dawn of life
 986 on Earth (e.g.: the conversion rate between information $-H-$ and eco-kinetic energy $-E_e-$ for unicellular marine algae is
 987 only of $k_e = 1.3806504\mathbf{E-10}$ J_e.nat/individual, and the corresponding minimum change of energy level per individual is
 988 $h_e^{ec} = 6.62606957\mathbf{E-13}$ J_e.nat/individual). This means that tiny unicellular organisms add tiny “bricks” to increase the
 989 evolutionary building of life (increase of C_s). Meanwhile, larger multicellular eukaryotic organisms add larger bricks
 990 (e.g.: $k_e = 1.3806504\mathbf{E+2}$ J_e.nat/individual, and $h_e^{ec} = 6.62606957\mathbf{E-01}$ J_e.nat/individual for ruderal vegetation). For
 991 instance, the correlation coefficient between niche area per species per survey (calculated as $(\sigma_{H_p} \times \sigma_{E_e}) / S_T$) and m_{ep} is r
 992 $= 0.986$, $p = 7.44\mathbf{E-14}$ ($N = 18$; 2 surveys under non-stationary conditions and 2 outliers were excluded). This is in
 993 agreement with the significant slowness of the Precambrian evolution (it embraces roughly seven-eighths of the Earth's
 994 history) in comparison with the Post-Cambrian stage (the last 541 million years $\approx 11.76\%$ of the Earth's history)
 995 characterized by the evolution of larger and more complex organisms.

996 From previous sections, ecological stacking per eco-evolutionary blocks is constrained within a range of total
 997 species diversity (H_T) values per survey between 0 and $H_{Tmax} \approx 5.64$ nat/individual (see Fig. 3b). Thus, if it is true that
 998 the increase of body size is associated with the eco-evolutionary improvement of life, then the level of eco-evolutionary
 999 performance (E_{vp}) assessed as the ratio

$$1000 \quad C_s / H_{Tmax} = \sigma_{E_e} / (\sigma_{H_p} \times H_{Tmax}) = E_{vp} \quad (19)$$

1001 per eco-evolutionary block should be directly correlated with m_e (see Fig. 11a).

1002 According to Fig. 11a (with $r = 0.99$; $p < 0.00001$):

$$1003 \quad E_{vp} = -a + bx = -4.937 + \underline{661.974} \times m_e \quad (20)$$

1004 For $a = -4.937$ in comparison with $a = 0$: $t = -1.64686$ with $p = 0.12 > 0.05$. Then it is possible to take $a = 0$ in Eq.
 1005 (20), and Eq. (19) would be explained as a linear increase of the product $h_e^{ec} \times m_e$, with $h_e^{ec} = 6.62606957\mathbf{E0}$

1006 $J_e \cdot \text{nat}/\text{individual}$ (see Section 2.1), being $\varphi = 2$ (E_{vp} , mean observed value = 26.29; E_{vp} , mean expected value from $h_e^{ec} \times$
1007 $m_e = 31.25$; $t = -0.187$, $p = 0.853$). The equations of regression for C_s/H_{Tmax} vs. m_e , and $c_{e,max} - l_t$ (see Fig. 3a) vs. m_e in
1008 Fig. 11a are very similar to each other. According to Section 4.1, $c_{e,max} - l_t$ indicates the difference between the niche's
1009 fragment that belongs to stretch 2 (from l_t to $c_{e,max}$ in Fig. 3a, or from l_t' to l_s in Fig. 3a) and the niche's fragment that
1010 belongs to stretch 1 (from 0 to l_t in Fig. 3a, or from $H_T = 0$ to H_T, l_t' in Fig. 3b).

1011 As a result, the above-commented similarity between both regression equations supports that in the same measure in
1012 which m_e increases, the performance of ecological niche depends more and more of ecological factors. In other words,
1013 the evolutionary process expands the capability of ecological resources exploitation of species (Eq. (19)) simultaneously
1014 to their average body size. But this implies an evolutionary shift from stretch 1 to stretch 2 (from genetic to
1015 environmental factors). So, if we use genetic indicators to explore the correlation body size \leftrightarrow evolutionary rate there is
1016 a trend to obtain opposite correlations, because *our indicator selection goes in the opposite direction of the eco-*
1017 *evolutionary process*. Contrastingly, if we use phenotypic-fossil-paleontological indicators there is a trend in favor of
1018 obtaining direct correlations body size \leftrightarrow evolutionary rate, because *our indicator selection goes in the same direction*
1019 *of the eco-evolutionary process*. This explains why there is a bias about the association between body size and
1020 evolutionary rate depending on the type of indicator selected ($\chi^2 = 7.14$, $p = 0.0076$, see above in this section).

1021 It is clear at this point that the emergence of degenerate ecological states means a sudden jump in regard to eco-
1022 kinetic energy values (i.e., preferable occupancy of the lowest and the highest levels of E_e with an empty space in
1023 between) with the successional glide of the ecosystem toward lower values of σ_{Hp} , (higher partition of species diversity
1024 values). Since there is a complementarity $E_e \leftrightarrow H_p$, then the above-mentioned empty space in regard to E_e should have
1025 an equivalent reflection in regard to H_p ' values, and this results in the emergence of an area of minimum habitability or
1026 eco-pause in the H_p ', E_e scalar field of ecological niche assessed at the eco-evolutionary block level. Besides,
1027 degenerate ecological states emerge because a stationary ecosystem works as a cavity resonator (a sort of ecological
1028 cage due to the influence of B-D_{TO-H}, see Section 2.1). Therefore, from the biogeographic point of view, the emergence
1029 of degenerate ecological states and eco-pauses should be reinforced when any stationary ecosystem is additionally
1030 limited from the spatial point of view because it is located in a strongly insular area (i.e., the ecosystem is a small cage
1031 within a larger one, the island, which is not significantly larger than the ecosystem itself). The opposite phenomenon
1032 should occur in continental areas due to the same reason. After all, the emergence of h_e^{ec} depends on a phenomenon of
1033 ecological diffraction (wave interference) between waves of S and waves of J' (see Fig. 1) that are correlated with
1034 waves of trophic production and waves of trophic consumption, respectively (see Rodríguez et al., 2015c). But physical
1035 diffraction, on the one hand, is particularly reinforced in regard to deploy a well-defined succession of noticeable
1036 differences between minimums and maximums of wave amplitude (A_w) of the wavefront when waves encounter an
1037 obstacle, or a slit, with a size (o_s ; obstacle's size) that is comparable in size to their wavelength (see Fig. 11b).
1038 Meanwhile, on the other hand, diffraction is smoothed when $o_s \gg \lambda$ (see Fig. 11c in comparison with 11b). The
1039 ecological equivalent to this obstacle is an isolated territory with an enough small size to be closer to the ecological
1040 wavelength (λ_e) typical of a given continental taxocene that has emitted the original eco-evolutionary wave able to
1041 produce a successful insular colonization. All in all, this interaction should be understood as an ecological modification
1042 of the Huygens principle in physics: every point (macrostate) on the original wavefront acts as a source (due to the
1043 combination of reproduction and dispersal) of secondary ecological waves that interfere with each other, spreading
1044 forward with approximately the same speed of the original wave. If the first wave source points are abundant (as in Fig.

1045 11c, a simple model of biological invasion in a continental area), the interference level will be high, by blurring the
1046 wave pattern in such a magnitude that the secondary wave front will be almost a simple line. On the contrary, if the first
1047 wave source points are scarce (as in Fig. 11b, a simple model of biological invasion in an insular area), then the wave-
1048 like nature of the ecosystem functioning becomes clearer.

1049 In other words, the wonderful and so conspicuous set of evidences in favor of natural selection that Darwin found in
1050 the Galapagos Islands is more related with the similarity of size between insular territories and the physical deployment
1051 of λ_e in space, than with the direct effects of geographic isolation that interrupts the genetic flow between populations.
1052 Speaking in statistical terms, quantum ecological uncertainty indicates that the cause-effect chain of natural selection
1053 theory that connects (1) insularity \rightarrow (2) interruption of genetic flow \rightarrow (3) genetic differentiation between populations
1054 until reaching speciation processes, it is under the underlying influence of statistical spuriousness due to a bias of
1055 omitted variable (DeMaris 2004, pp. 98-100): there is a fourth factor neglected so far (the reinforcement of ecological
1056 diffraction due to the similarity between insular space and the physical deployment of λ_e) that accounts for the
1057 evolutionary meaning of these three parameters as a whole.

1058 As a result, it is expectable a more noticeable emergence of eco-pauses in insular areas than in continental areas
1059 (compare Fig. 11d with 11e). Given that $E_e = \frac{1}{2} \text{body size} \times I_e^2$, then eco-pauses have a correspondent reflection on
1060 distributions of the mean value of body size per plot more biased in favor of edge values (statistical predominance of
1061 dwarf and giant mean body sizes per plot, with noticeable scarcity of intermediate sizes) in insular ecosystems than in
1062 continental ecosystems (compare Fig. 11g with 11h, respectively); e.g.: “*The body size–frequency distribution [of*
1063 *lizards at the world scale] is highly modal and right skewed ... Insular lizards tend towards both extremes of the size*
1064 *spectrum*” (Meiri, 2008). The significantly larger relative size of insular eco-pauses (see Fig. 11f) also implies the
1065 performance of ecological niches with a lower degree of compaction (i.e., a more friable ecological functioning that
1066 allows an easier infiltration from the outside). This is coherent with the fact that oceanic islands appear to be
1067 particularly vulnerable to the impact of invasive species (Denslow, 2003; Berglund et al., 2009; Kueffer et al., 2009).

1068 The transfer of an ecosystem as a whole from a continental territory to an insular one is impossible at all; on the
1069 contrary, insular colonization takes place slowly, by isolated elements with a heterogeneous origin which arrive at
1070 different states of the insular ecological development. Besides, the allowed positions of E_e values in the H_p' , E_e scalar
1071 field should be *filled always from bottom to top*, either at the evolutionary or ecological scale, because this is the only
1072 way to minimize the number of vacant energy positions in order to maximize the efficiency of ecosystem in regard to
1073 energy consumption (e.g., this law is also valid to fill electronic levels in the atomic realm). If an invasive species has a
1074 large body size and it successfully arrives in an early state of insular evolution (low partition of H_p' 's gradients), then its
1075 migration is equivalent to a transfer from Fig. 7d to 7b, or from Fig. 6f to 6d. Thus, the eco-evolutionary pressures in
1076 favor of a large body size (high E_e value) due to a high degree of partition of H_p' 's gradients would have disappeared
1077 (i.e.: “ecological relaxation” or “ecological release” according to Whittaker and Fernández-Palacios, 2007, pp. 173–
1078 174). In this case, for instance, the difference between $M_{d(h)}$ in Fig. 7d and M_d in Fig. 7b (i.e.: $5.18 = 7.28 - 2.1$) means
1079 an irrelevant surplus of energy that could be difficult to sustain under insularity conditions. In this case the most
1080 suitable option is to evolve toward dwarfism, since under ecological conditions similar to those of Fig. 6d it is sure that
1081 there will be availability of free low energy levels. On the contrary, if a small-bodied species performs a successful
1082 transference in the opposite direction (from low to high partition of H_p' 's gradients: from 7b to 7d) then the most
1083 powerful selective pressures would be in favor of gigantism. The ecological reality is more complex than these typical
1084 examples due to unpredictable collateral influences. However, the emergence of degenerate ecological states is strongly

1085 linked to the calculation of Eq. (18). Besides, since any ecological transfer between different territories implies some
 1086 kind of ecological gradient, the probability of evolution toward either dwarfism or gigantism in islands can be
 1087 summarized, at least in the first instance, in the following way:

1088 $C_s(\text{continental}) - C_s(\text{insular}) = \Delta C_s > 0 \rightarrow$ higher probability of evolutionary shift toward dwarfism in large-bodied foreign
 1089 species; i.e.: the invasive species “drifts” toward the left lower border of e_{cp} (see Fig. 11d, e) per eco-evolutionary block
 1090 because there is a higher relative availability of vacant positions at low levels of eco-kinetic energy. (21.1)

1091 $C_s(\text{continental}) - C_s(\text{insular}) = \Delta C_s \approx 0 \rightarrow$ neutral evolution in regard to body size; i.e.: there is a random distribution of
 1092 invasive species along the border of e_{cp} per eco-evolutionary block, or even within the e_{cp} , given that the invasive
 1093 species comes from an environment with alien (non-insular) evolutionary pressures. (21.2)

1094 $C_s(\text{continental}) - C_s(\text{insular}) = \Delta C_s < 0 \rightarrow$ higher probability of evolutionary shift toward gigantism in small-bodied foreign
 1095 species, i.e.: the invasive species “drifts” toward the right upper border of e_{cp} per eco-evolutionary block because there
 1096 is a lower relative availability of vacant positions at low levels of eco-kinetic energy. (21.3)

1097 For example, it is plausible to assume that Eq. (21.2) should match with the point of balance between immigration
 1098 and extinction rates that determines the insular equilibrium in regard to species number foreseen by the model of
 1099 MacArthur and Wilson (1967; see also Warren et al., 2015). However, k_e and h_e^{ec} have a discontinuous behavior
 1100 between eco-evolutionary blocks, and both variables affect the particular expression of C_s (Eq. (18)). So it is difficult to
 1101 accept that a given oceanic island has a single general equilibrium point that is simultaneously reached by the set of
 1102 insular species as a whole, instead off several points of equilibrium that are non-synchronous with each other in
 1103 accordance with the spectrum of eco-evolutionary blocks that have successfully arrived to the island from the mainland.
 1104 In such a way, the noticeable shift of body size during the process of insular colonization on the part of continental
 1105 species (a graded trend for continental immigrant species toward insular gigantism in small species, as well as in favor
 1106 of insular dwarfism in larger species; a.k.a. “the island rule”; see van Valen, 1973; Lomolino, 2005; Whittaker and
 1107 Fernández-Palacios, 2007, p. 190) can be explained as a probabilistic effect of quantum ecological uncertainty.
 1108

1109 4.3.3 Quantum ecological uncertainty and the socio-economic exploitation of natural resources

1110 Energy consumption is essential to obtain information (i.e., knowledge embodied in a network of socio-economic
 1111 functions, in the social case) for any kind of system capable to keep a position far away from equilibrium. This explains
 1112 why civilization is obsessed with energy supply (see Odum, 2007). Such an insatiable hunger for socially useful energy
 1113 (E_s) depends on the increment of power (energy flow per time unit) which, in turn, has two dimensions: **(a)** total amount
 1114 of energy taken away from nature, and **(b)** supply stability (reduction of σ_{E_s}). However, from the fulfillment of Eq. (14)
 1115 with $\Theta_e = E_e$ and $\Omega_e = H_p$, it is impossible to reduce σ_{E_s} (i.e., E_e transferred from nature to society) without increasing
 1116 σ_{H_p} . Understanding the meaning of this result for biological conservation needs additional explanations.

1117 Adding information to our cultural patrimony involves sharing a limited planetary endowment of energy by
 1118 converting either E_e (e.g.: fire wood, foods, etc.) or ancient H_p (since fossil fuels are the species diversity of ancient
 1119 ecosystems geologically transformed into oil and coal; see Kvenvolden, 2006), with our natural surroundings. But this
 1120 transfer $E_e \rightarrow E_s$ needs certain modification of natural ecosystems in order to guarantee a low value of σ_{E_s} . According
 1121 to Section 2.1 (see the concept of B-D_{TO-H}), the performance of an ecological assemblage as shown in Fig. 12a (data
 1122 from survey rv4, from overtone 1 to overtone 14), it is supported by a gradient of decreasing availability of energy per
 1123 unit of biomass (i.e., $E_e/m_{eT} = J_e/kg$) from **(a)** macrostates with small-bodied organisms that are very abundant, with a

1124 high biotic potential and tolerant to overcrowding (*r*-strategy) to **(b)** macrostates of organisms with diametrically
1125 opposite traits (*K*-strategy). The degree of compaction (λ_e fluctuations) of the stationary trophic information waves
1126 (STIW_s in Fig. 1) that travel between these two edges yields a background of interspecific pressures. Such a
1127 background produces degenerate ecological states and eco-pauses (e_{cp}) which, in turn, are essential to promote the
1128 increase of total species diversity (H_T) in the long run.

1129 But the ideal organisms (either plants or animals) for being industrially bred with economic exploitation goals are a
1130 sort of unnatural combination of both edges (*r* and *K*) whose statistical coordinates in the H_p', E_e scalar field *do not exist*
1131 *under natural condition*. That is to say, civilization needs breeds that are very abundant, with a high biotic potential, and
1132 very tolerant to overcrowding, but also with large-bodied organisms: ecological monsters $r \times K$. Besides, the
1133 background of interspecific pressure needs to be suppressed by using monocultures, pesticides, herbicides, and livestock
1134 isolation in order to increase the agribusiness yield. If we combine these production requirements, then we obtain a
1135 suitable state of socio-economic exploitation that depends on a convergence of trends between I_e and m_{ep} toward
1136 maximum values under conditions in which $S \rightarrow 1$, and $H_T \rightarrow 0$. That is to say, a suitable state of socio-economic
1137 exploitation is only compatible with an “ecological anti-wave” in the H_p', E_e scalar field with wave amplitude $\rightarrow 0$ and
1138 $\lambda_e \rightarrow 0$ or, in other words: an ecological wave collapse. Finally, this suitable state of socio-economic exploitation is
1139 expanded in space and time in order to minimize σ_{E_s} , by increasing the uncertainty in regard to species diversity values
1140 (increase of $\sigma_{H_p'}$) due to the fragmentation, isolation and replacement of those natural systems of high species diversity
1141 in which $H_T \gg 0$; $\Delta H_p' \gg 0$; wave amplitude $\gg 0$; $\lambda_e \gg 0$; $\sigma_{H_p'} \rightarrow$ minimum; and $\sigma_{E_e} \rightarrow$ maximum.

1142 For example, wheat (*Triticum aestivum*) is a type of weed whose development has been backed up by civilization.
1143 Ruderal vegetation (rv) is the wild taxocenosis eco-evolutionarily closest to wheat included in this paper. In survey rv4,
1144 from o_1 to o_{14} (values per macrostate): $H_p' (\text{mean value}) = 1.31$ nat/individual; $m_e \text{ max.} = 0.1127$ kg/individual; $I_e (\text{mean value}) =$
1145 60.23 d; $I_e \text{ max.} = 87.66$ d; $E_e (\text{mean value}) = 81.34$ J_e/individual; and $E_e \text{ max.} = 376.5$ J_e/individual. However, yield of wheat
1146 has been genetically improved by increasing seed number and/or weight by producing a 31% increase in total biomass
1147 per plant (Šramková et al., 2009, p. 37) under monoculture conditions. If we applied an equivalent improvement to
1148 rv4, then $H_p' (\text{mean value}) \approx 0.0$ nat/individual; $m_e \text{ max.} = 0.1476$ (since $((0.1127 \times 31\%) / 100\%) + 0.1127 = 0.1476$); $I_e (\text{mean}$
1149 $\text{value}) \rightarrow 193.92$ d; and E_e (single value due to monoculture conditions) = $\frac{1}{2} 0.1476 \times 193.92^2 = 2775.94$ J_e/individual. With
1150 these new values, Fig. 12a would change to Fig. 12b; or equivalently in a 3D chart in which $x = H_p'$, $y = m_e$, and $z = I_e$;
1151 rv4 would change from Fig. 12c to Fig. 12d. And this modification has been repeated all over the world in regard to
1152 hundreds of species of agricultural interest for thousands of years ago.

1153 It is considered in physics that a quantum system simultaneously exists in the whole of its possible states (quantum
1154 superposition) but, when a measurement is performed on the system, then only one of the possible configurations
1155 emerges. For instance, the system behaves either like a particle or a like wave (wave-particle duality, depending on the
1156 type of measurement, since both states cannot be observed in a single experiment), or it remains in only one of the
1157 whole of its possible harmonics despite the system, under undisturbed circumstance (without measurement), it is
1158 simultaneously functioning in many harmonics. Therefore, only two kinds of mutually excluding “measurements” can
1159 be performed in regard to nature-society interaction: **(a)** minimally-invasive observations in which scientific
1160 information is collected without ecological wave collapse; or **(b)** socio-economic “observations” in which energy is
1161 taken away from nature by producing an ecological wave collapse in order to minimize σ_{E_s} , by collaterally maximizing
1162 $\sigma_{H_p'}$ as a secondary effect (i.e., loss of species diversity) due to the ecological fulfillment of quantum uncertainty

1163 principle. In such a sense, even the very common concept of *agro-ecosystem* is an oxymoron in itself because “*agro*”
1164 refers to a coherent particle-like fraction devoid of spontaneous evolutionary capability; but “*ecosystem*” refers to a
1165 decoherent wave-like fraction with capability to evolve by spontaneously producing degenerate ecological states.

1166

1167 **References**

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1410 **FIGURE CAPTIONS:**

1411 **Fig. 1** Graphical explanation of key elements about the quantum understanding of ecosystem functioning according
 1412 to Rodríguez et al., 2015c. **(a)** Typical statistical density distribution of H_p (see Eq. (1) and Eq. (2)) starting from data
 1413 in Appendix B, survey ma2 (marine microalgae), rows 317-341. H_p' : class mark (midpoint) of the respective category
 1414 of H_p values. K-S and χ^2 : goodness of fit tests in comparison with the standard gamma distribution (black line). **(b)**
 1415 Oscillations obtained from the distribution in panel (a) in order to assess quantum parameters per macrostate (M). ρ_e :
 1416 richness oscillations, or trophic production curve, (cubic spline fit based on standardized $-xs-$ values starting from
 1417 original values of S per M). S : species number (richness). τ_e : evenness oscillations, or trophic consumption curve (cubic
 1418 spline fit based on standardized $-xs-$ values starting from original values of J' per M). J' : evenness index of Pielou
 1419 (1969) per M : $J'_M = H_M/\ln S_M$; where H_M : total species diversity (Eq. (1)) per M . $STIW$: stationary trophic information
 1420 wave ($\rho_e - \tau_e$). λ_e : ecological wavelength per $M =$ twice the distance ($2 \times 0.5\lambda_e$) between two successive crests or
 1421 troughs. **(c)** Result from the calculations to obtain h_e^{ec} per individual per M (see Eq. (10)). **(d1 - d2)** Two examples of
 1422 H_p distributions with a different number of categories. **(e1-e2)** The respective overtones (o_i) or vibration modes (1 –
 1423 fundamental harmonic– & 16, respectively; h_e^{ec} is constant for the spectrum of overtones as a whole) from distributions
 1424 in d1 and d2. A : antinodes. N : nodes. L_N : line of nodes (trophic equilibrium level). $STIW+$: positive trophic polarity ($\rho_e -$
 1425 τ_e). $STIW-$: negative trophic polarity ($\tau_e - \rho_e$). Overtone numbers ($o_i \#$) are given by the number of antinodes per
 1426 vibration mode. Cubic spline fits to obtain oscillations were performed by using TableCurve 2D Version 5.01
 1427 (SYSTAT, 2002). Mean comparisons were performed by using Statistica–6 for Windows (StatSoft, Inc., 2001). Primer–
 1428 5.2.9 (Primer-E Ltd., 2002) was used to calculate diversity indicators. Additional details in Rodríguez et al. (2015c).
 1429

1430 **Fig. 2** Statistical tests in favor of quantum ecological uncertainty taken “cor” as a prototypical survey. **(a)**
 1431 Correlation between the standard deviation of individual eco-kinetic energy values (σ_{Ee}) per macrostate and overtone
 1432 number (o_i). **(b)** Correlation between the standard deviation of species diversity values ($\sigma_{Hp'}$) per macrostate and
 1433 overtone number. **(c)** Trade-off type correlation between σ_{Ee} and $\sigma_{Hp'}$ (first requisite for the fulfillment of quantum
 1434 ecological uncertainty, strictly speaking). **(d)** Difference between the mean value of $\sigma_{Ee} \cdot \sigma_{Hp'}$ and $0.5h_e^{ec}/2\pi$ (second
 1435 requisite for the fulfillment of quantum ecological uncertainty, strictly speaking). **(e)** Correlation that shows that
 1436 quantum ecological uncertainty ($\sigma_{Ee} \cdot \sigma_{Hp'}$) cannot be compensated by performing ecological measurements under
 1437 conditions of low dispersion of ecological wavelength values (σ_{λ_e}).

1438 **Fig. 3** Relationships between quantum ecological uncertainty and species richness per overtone. **(a)** Correlation
 1439 between $\sigma_{Ee} \cdot \sigma_{Hp'}$ and the mean number of species per macrostate (μS_M) in survey “cor”. $(\frac{1}{2}h_e^{ec}/2\pi, S_c) = (5.2728E-5,$

1440 16.504): border value (according to Eq. (14)) or threshold level (l_t) between ecological certainty (c : $\mu S_M < S_c$) and
 1441 uncertainty (u : $\mu S_M > S_c$) about ecological niche assessment (see Eq. (15)) with reference to a bidimensional functional
 1442 space H_p, E_e . $c_{e, \max}$: forecasted level of maximum ecological compaction: when the internal fluctuations of the system
 1443 reach an overtone as high as possible (e.g.: see Fig. 1e2 in comparison with Fig. 1e1) and there is no species (notice that
 1444 $\mu S_M = 0$ for $c_{e, \max}$) capable to endure so high coexistence level. $c_{e, \max}$ is, at the intra-survey level, the point equivalent to
 1445 l_s (see below) at the inter-taxonomic or inter-survey level. Every small square in the scatter plot is an overtone. **(b)**
 1446 Correlation between the number of species living under uncertainty conditions in the ecological niche assessment ($S_u =$
 1447 $S_T - S_c$; where S_T : total species number per survey) expressed as a percentage of S_T (see Eq. (16)), and H_T per survey. r :
 1448 linear correlation $H_T, S_u\%$ with intercept (a) $\neq 0$. r' : linear correlation $H_T, S_u\%$ with $a = 0$. H_T : total species diversity per
 1449 survey. l_t' : threshold level (l_t) between ecological certainty (c : $\mu S_M < S_c$) and uncertainty (u : $\mu S_M > S_c$) for survey “cor”
 1450 expressed in terms of $H_T, S_u\%$ coordinates. l_s : ecological saturation level ($H_T, S_u\% = 5.640, 100$; according to Eq. (17)).
 1451 l_o : metastable zone of ecological oversaturation. Every small circle in the scatter plot is a survey.

1452

1453 **Fig. 4** Two tessellations of $H_{p(\mu)}, E_{e(\mu)}$ scalar fields of equal size by means of Voronoi lines for the whole set of
 1454 species for two surveys with different values of total species diversity (H_T) but equal values of k_e (see Eq. (2)) and h_e^{ec}
 1455 (see Eq. (10)). **(a)** Tessellation for survey “cor” ($H_T = 1.795$ nat/individual). **(b)** Tessellation for survey “pli” ($H_T =$
 1456 3.262 nat/individual). Each black square is a species. Grey lines: Voronoi lines (see Okabe et al., 2000) that divide the
 1457 H_p, E_e scalar field between the individual data points. The division is such that each of the data points is surrounded by
 1458 boundaries including only the area that is closer to its respective “center” data point than to any other data point. The
 1459 enclosed area per point is equivalent to the respective ecological niche per species according to its H_p and E_e values.

1460

1461 **Fig. 5** Increase of the degree of inter-specific linkage between two (1 and 2) hypothetical ecological assemblages
 1462 (A_e) across the statistical association between H_T (Eq. (1) at the survey level) and $S_u\%$ (see Eq. (17) and Fig. 3b). l_t :
 1463 threshold level ($0.5 \cdot h_e^{ec}, S_c$) between certainty and uncertainty in regard to ecological niche assessment. l_s : saturation
 1464 level (5.640, 100% according to Eq. (17)). l_o : metastable zone of oversaturation level and maximum uncertainty in
 1465 which ecological niche performance takes place at the sub-species or intra-population level (see Section 4.1). H_p : Eq.
 1466 (1) at the plot (μ) level, mean value per species group (S_M) per macrostate (category of H_p values in Fig. 1a). E_e : mean
 1467 eco-kinetic energy per individual (see Eq. (4)). μ : mean; σ : standard deviation. See additional explanations in main text.

1468

1469 **Fig. 6** Effects of overtone fluctuations on indicators of species coexistence. **(a)-(c)** Convergence of scalar
 1470 indicators of coexistence (i.e., without reference to a given position in the H_p, E_e space) either from low to high
 1471 overtones (o_i) or for low to high degrees of ecological uncertainty ($\sigma_{H_p}, \sigma_{E_e}$). CV_{E_e} : coefficient of variation of individual
 1472 eco-kinetic energy values per macrostate per distribution of H_p values (ED_H). CV_{H_p} : coefficient of variation of species
 1473 diversity values per macrostate per ED_H . σ_{H_p} and σ_{E_e} : standard deviation of species diversity and individual eco-kinetic
 1474 energy values per ED_H , respectively. **(d)-(e)-(f)** Partition per macrostates (black dots) of a constant ($0 \rightarrow 2, 0 \rightarrow 0.5$)
 1475 ecological scalar field H_p', E_e for overtones (o_i) 1, 7, and 16, respectively; survey “cor”. **o_1** : $H_p' = 0.99_{(\mu) \pm 0.67_{(\sigma)}}$,
 1476 $CV_{H_p} = 66.67\%$; and $E_e = 0.08_{(\mu) \pm 0.01_{(\sigma)}}$, $CV_{E_e} = 13.34\%$. **o_7** : $H_p' = 0.96_{(\mu) \pm 0.52_{(\sigma)}}$, $CV_{H_p} = 53.99\%$; and $E_e =$
 1477 $0.085_{(\mu) \pm 0.03_{(\sigma)}}$, $CV_{E_e} = 39.41\%$. **o_{16}** : $H_p' = 0.96_{(\mu) \pm 0.46_{(\sigma)}}$, $CV_{H_p} = 47.44\%$; and $E_e = 0.10_{(\mu) \pm 0.10_{(\sigma)}}$, $CV_{E_e} = 93.40\%$.
 1478 Grey lines: Voronoi lines (see explanation in Fig. 4 caption) that delimit ecological niches at the guild (macrostate)

1479 level. M_d : degenerate macrostate; see additional explanations in main text. **(g)-(h)** Analyses, equivalent to the previous
 1480 ones, in regard to species included in the macrostate of maximum total eco-kinetic energy (E_{eT} , see Eq. (4)) per
 1481 distribution of H_p values for overtones 1 and 16, respectively. **σ_1** : $H_p' = 1.037_{(\mu)} \pm 0.150_{(\sigma)}$, $CV_{H_p} = 14.47\%$; and $E_e =$
 1482 $0.065_{(\mu)} \pm 0.039_{(\sigma)}$, $CV_{E_e} = 61.55\%$. **σ_{16}** : $H_p' = 0.688_{(\mu)} \pm 0.004_{(\sigma)}$, $CV_{H_p} = 0.57\%$; and $E_e = 0.134_{(\mu)} \pm 0.099_{(\sigma)}$, $CV_{E_e} =$
 1483 74.63% . Aa: *Agaricia agaricites*; Ag: *Agaricia grahamae*; Ah: *Agaricia humilis*; Al: *Agaricia lamarcki*; Cn:
 1484 *Colpophyllia natans*; Dc: *Diploria clivosa*; Ds: *Diploria strigosa*; Md: *Madracis decactis*; Ma: *Montastraea annularis*;
 1485 Mc: *Montastraea cavernosa*; Mfa: *Montastraea faveolata*; Mfr: *Montastraea franksi*; Msp: *Montastraea sp.*; Ml:
 1486 *Mycetophyllia lamarckiana*; Od: *Oculina diffusa*; Pa: *Porites astreoides*; Pp: *Porites porites*; Sr: *Siderastrea radians*;
 1487 Ss: *Siderastrea siderea*; Si: *Stephanocoenia intercepta*; Sm: *Stephanocoenia michelinii*. Arrows indicate two apparent
 1488 cases of commonly shared ecological niches in regard to this particular scalar field between Mfr and Md in (g), as well
 1489 as between Sr and Dc in (h). **(i)** Trade-off type correlation σ_{H_p} , σ_{E_e} (i.e., ecological uncertainty –see Fig. 2c– but in this
 1490 case in regard to species included within a commonly shared macrostate – M – of maximum total eco-kinetic energy –
 1491 E_{eT} , Eq. (4)– per overtone – σ_i), based on the same kind of data used to obtain (g)-(h), for the all of the overtones of
 1492 survey “cor”. Fig. 2c is the figure equivalent to (i) at the macrostate level. r : Pearson’s correlation coefficient. R :
 1493 Spearman’s correlation coefficient. Dashed line: adjustment by distance-weighted least squares.
 1494

1495 **Fig. 7** Emergence of degenerate macrostates (M_d , or degenerate ecological states: DESs) because of the functional
 1496 equivalence between the combination of quantum uncertainty \leftrightarrow CEP, in ecology, and the combination quantum
 1497 uncertainty \leftrightarrow Pauli exclusion principle, in physics. **(a)** Analysis of extremes for mean values of eco-kinetic energy per
 1498 macrostate (E_{eM}) based on empirical data of tree surveys of ruderal vegetation (rv) with the same values of h_e^{ec} and k_e .
 1499 Extremes values from (a) were taken as possible M_d s for survey rv8 (panel **(b)**); rv9 (panel **(c)**), and rv4 (panel **(d)**). The
 1500 emergence of M_d s is more noticeable with the net increase of overtone number (σ_i : $18 \rightarrow 19 \rightarrow 22$) and total species
 1501 diversity (H_T : from 1.707 to 2.405), despite the decreasing value of total eco-kinetic energy per survey (E_{eT} : $1.79E+5$
 1502 $\rightarrow 1.75E+5 \rightarrow 4.14E+4$). μE_{eM} : mean general background value of E_{eM} for the overtone as a whole. μE_{eM_d} : mean value
 1503 of E_e for those macrostates regarded as DES. h : macrostate regarded as highly degenerate ($E_{e,M_d(h)}/\mu E_{eM} = 7.28$) in
 1504 comparison with its ecological background in spite of being below the minimum value ($E_{e,M_d(h)}/\mu E_{eM} \geq 10$) for a
 1505 transitional jump between two different contiguous values of h_e^{ec} .
 1506

1507 **Fig. 8** Main theoretically expected elements for a typical macroevolutionary jump (dotted line) between two
 1508 contiguous eco-evolutionary blocks starting from the interaction between ecological uncertainty and CEP explained in
 1509 previous sections. Gray box: combined taxocenosis’s niche area ($\sigma_{H_p} \times \sigma_{E_e}$) for surveys of ruderal vegetation (rv) 9, 8
 1510 and 4. Gray dots: mean positions (i.e., μ_{H_p} , μ_{E_e} coordinates) into the scalar field per survey (9, 8 & 4, from left to right).
 1511 Gray lines: oscillations within the taxocenosis’s niche area similar to those fluctuations shown in Fig. 7. Black box and
 1512 lines: parameters, equivalent to the previous ones, for a survey of Mediterranean shrubland (Ms). DES: degenerate
 1513 ecological state. h_e^{ec} : value of the ecological equivalent of Planck’s constant per survey. E_{eM} : mean value of individual
 1514 eco-kinetic energy per individual per macrostate from overtones 1 to 14. H_p' : mean value of the class mark of species
 1515 diversity values per macrostate from overtones 1 to 14. $A_{e,(r)}$: transition macrostate in complete functional redundancy
 1516 (i.e., in full internal resonance in comparison with the quasi-resonance of micro-model 5 in Fig. 5) from rv to Ms. σ_w :
 1517 area of wave overlap (i.e., inter-block control by wave interference) between both eco-evolutionary blocks.

1518

1519 **Fig. 9** Empirical examples (based on data from survey “cor”) of some of the wave micro-models for interspecific
1520 relationships shown in Fig. 5. **(a)** Pearson’s linear correlation (r) between ecological uncertainty ($\sigma_{E_e} \cdot \sigma_{H_p}$) and the area
1521 (integral) under the cubic spline adjustment curve of E_e values as a function of H_p ’ values for several ecological
1522 assemblages at different hierarchical levels. Cubic spline fits and integrals were calculated by using TableCurve 2D
1523 Version 5.01 (SYSTAT, 2002). $\forall Sp.$, $\forall o_i$: coordinate for the all of the species set, across the whole spectrum of
1524 overtones. $\forall Sp., o_{14}$: coordinate for the all of the species set, fourteenth overtone. Od: *Oculina diffusa*. Pa: *Porites*
1525 *astreoides*. Cn: *Colpophyllia natans*. Sr: *Siderastrea radians*. Ss: *S. siderea*. Mc: *Montastraea cavernosa*. Mfa: *M.*
1526 *faveolata*. Dc: *Diploria clivosa*. Ds: *D. strigosa*. **(b)** Niche differentiation between two species in regard to their general
1527 ecological background ($\forall Sp.$). **(c)** Empirical example of pattern 5 in Fig. 5. **(d)** & **(e)** Empirical examples of pattern 3 in
1528 Fig. 5. **(f)** Empirical example of pattern 1 in Fig. 5. E_e : mean value of individual eco-kinetic energy per macrostate. H_p ’:
1529 class mark (midpoint) per class of H_p values in the distribution of species diversity values of the fourteenth overtone. •
1530 & ◦: mean coordinates (H_p ’, E_e) for oscillations of the respective species.

1531

1532 **Fig. 10** Association between time span per stratigraphic stage and lower boundary per stage. Data from Cohen et al.
1533 (2013).

1534

1535 **Fig. 11** Eco-evolutionary effects linked to the reinforcement of quantum ecological uncertainty under conditions of
1536 insularity. **(a)** Statistical associations of eco-evolutionary performance (E_{vp} , Eq. (19)) and the portion ($c_{e,max} \square l_i$) of
1537 ecological niche performed within life stretch #2 with the mean value of individual body size per plot (m_{ep}), including
1538 all of the stationary surveys. **(b)** & **(c)** The wave nature of a wave front (wf) with $\lambda = x_i$ is reinforced when wave
1539 diffraction takes place through a slit, or an obstacle, whose size $o_s \approx x_i$ **(b)**, and it is smoothed when $o_s \approx 5x_i$ **(c)**. I.e.: the
1540 huge size of quotidian objects and slits in comparison with the wavelength of light avoids that our vision would be quite
1541 blurred (in the opposite circumstances). **(d)** The size of eco-pause (e_{cp}) as a percentage of the total niche size (e_{nT})
1542 assessed at the survey level is magnified under insular conditions (survey “cor”: relatively small keys of coral reefs
1543 isolated from each other by different ecological conditions in the coast of Veracruz, Mexico) in comparison with
1544 continental conditions: Mediterranean shrubland in **(e)**. Each black dot is a macrostate that belongs to a particular
1545 overtone given a distribution of H_p values. **(f)** Mean comparison (Mann-Whitney U Test) of the relative percentage size
1546 of e_{cp} ($e_{cp}/e_{nT} \times 100$) between insular surveys and continental surveys. The bimodal nature (as statistical expression of
1547 the “island rule”) of the distribution of mean values of body size per plot (m_{ep}) is reinforced under insular conditions **(g)**
1548 in comparison with continental conditions **(h)**.

1549

1550 **Fig. 12** Ecological wave collapse (e.w.c.) due to farming activity understood as ecologically equivalent to a
1551 measurement process (in the quantum sense of the term). Ecological wave collapse of ruderal vegetation (survey rv4) in
1552 the H_p ’, E_e scalar field from natural conditions **(a)**, to a suitable state of socio-economic exploitation (SS-EE), in **(b)**,
1553 when the agricultural improvements developed for wheat crops are applied to its closest eco-evolutionary block. From
1554 **(c)** to **(d)**: The previous process represented in 3D at the macrostate (M) level.

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

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Fig. 8

Fig. 7 Main theoretically expected elements for a typical macroevolutionary jump (dotted line) between two contiguous eco-evolutionary blocks starting from the interaction between QEU and CEP explained in previous sections. Gray box: combined taxocenosis's niche area ($\sigma_{H_p} \times \sigma_{E_e}$) for surveys of ruderal vegetation (rv) 9, 8 and 4. Gray dots: mean positions (i.e., μ_{H_p}, μ_{E_e} coordinates) into the scalar field per survey (9, 8 & 4, from left to right). Gray lines: oscillations within the taxocenosis's niche area similar to those fluctuations shown in Fig. 7. Black box and lines: parameters, equivalent to the previous ones, for a survey of Mediterranean shrubland (Ms). DES: degenerate ecological state. h_e^{ec} : value of the ecological equivalent of Planck's constant per survey. E_{eM} : mean individual eco-kinetic energy per individual per macrostate from overtone number 1 to 14. H_p' : mean value of the class mark of species diversity values per macrostate from overtone number 1 to 14. $A_{e,t(r)}$: transition macrostate in full internal resonance (complete functional redundancy) from rv to Ms. o_w : area of wave overlap (i.e., inter-block control by wave interference) between both eco-evolutionary blocks.

Fig. 9

Fig. 10

Fig. 11

Fig. 12

